

Integrative Indian Knowledge Systems based approach for the health of a pregnant woman and developmental milestones of her child - a case study

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Abstract

In modern times, the focus is mostly on the physical health and fitness of future generations and to some extent on mental health, with very little emphasis given to the development of spiritual, emotional, and moral values. Due to this ignorance, the upcoming generation is becoming deprived of emotional, human and moral values, and is getting involved in different kinds of misconduct leading to degradation.

The founder/patron of All World Gayatri Pariwar, Yug Rishi Pandit Shriram Sharma Acharya ji has stated several methodologies, based on ancient Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS), for the virtuous development of the future generation. He directed that the foundation of the personality (body and mind) of a child is laid in the womb of the mother, and intervention at this stage can lead to the development of a civilized, cultured, and virtuous future generation, further leading to a well developed family, as well as the upliftment of the society, nation and the world.

All such inspiring efforts for the mental, emotional and spiritual development of future generations are combined under a systematic movement known as the “Aao Gadhe Sanskarwan Peedhi” program, run by Shantikunj, Haridwar, India, the headquarter of All World Gayatri Pariwar, wherein ‘Gharbhotsav Sanskar’ is conducted in the third month of pregnancy, and IKS based guidance on various aspects is administered to the pregnant woman and her family members throughout pregnancy, as well as after delivery.

This paper depicts one such case study of ‘Gharbhotsav Sanskar’ under the movement “Aao Gadhe Sanskarwan Peedhi”, in which the effect of basic teachings of ancient Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) on the physical, mental, emotional, moral and spiritual health of a pregnant woman, as well as on the developmental milestones of the child have been studied. Positive effects were observed after the pregnant woman started following an ideal daily routine, yogic exercises, pranayama, dhyana (meditation), diet (balanced, pious (sattvic), and virtuous (sanskrit)), dialogue with the fetus (womb conversation), etc., as per the guidelines given in this program. Also, several developmental milestones of the new born child happened much earlier (were preponed) as compared to the standard developmental milestones (as given by a USA based standard validated scale). It was also noticed that all the milestones for more than 12 months to 2 years were achieved by the child in less than or equal to 12 months, illustrating the effectiveness of this ancient IKS based methodology in the creation of an advanced offspring as compared to its normal peers. The results depict the

effectiveness of the basic elements of the ancient IKS, with regards to the creation of an advanced future generation.

Keywords: Aao Gadhe Sanskarwan Peedhi, Gharbhotsav Sanskar, Pregnant Woman, Future Generation, Indian Culture, Garbh Sanskar, Child Developmental Milestones

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1. Introduction

In contemporary society, the prevailing notion is that the socio-economic environment significantly influences the development of each generation (Francis & Hoefel, 2018). Generation Z, encompassing individuals born between 1996 and 2010 (Francis & Hoefel, 2018; Coe et al., 2022; Balchandani et al., 2023; Arora et al., 2022; Parker and Igielnik, 2020), is undergoing a subtle yet notable evolution. Their identity is deeply intertwined with socio-economic factors such as the digital era, the COVID-19 pandemic, and concerns about climate change (Francis & Hoefel, 2018; Sharma et al., 2024a). These factors have led to various behavioral health issues, including mental health disorders, a preference for virtual interactions over real-life relationships, and excessive reliance on social media (Francis and Hoefel, 2018; Sharma et al., 2024a).

Similarly, Generation Alpha, born between 2010 and 2025, is growing up in an era dominated by digital media, using technology from a very young age for entertainment and education (Brower, 2025; Smith et al., 2025; Doherty et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2024a). However, this early exposure has its drawbacks, as it often results in a lack of practical skills and hands-on experience, isolation, loneliness, exposure to digital media advertised life's priorities and threats, fear of being rendered jobless due to continuous technological advancements, etc., which makes them susceptible to mental health challenges (Brower, 2025; Smith et al., 2025; Doherty et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2024a).

India, with its notably young median age of 28, has a significant portion of the global Gen Z population (Skinner, 2022). Interestingly, employed Gen Z individuals in India exhibit distinct patterns related to health and burnout (Brassey et al., 2023). While they score well on various health metrics, they also experience significant levels of burnout, including exhaustion and cognitive impairment (Brassey et al., 2023). Addressing burnout and ensuring overall well-being pose ongoing challenges for them (Lufkin, 2021). It is no wonder then that both Gen Z and millennials are leading consumers of wellness products and services (Callaghan et al., 2024).

Delving deeper into the underlying causes of these trends, it becomes apparent that in contemporary upbringing, quite often adequate attention is not paid to spiritual, mental, emotional, and moral development (Lapsley, 2025; Raman & Thomas, 2023; Sharma & Singh, 2022). Consequently, children may lack essential values and qualities, leading to

mental and emotional challenges (Lapsley, 2025; Raman & Thomas, 2023; Sharma & Singh, 2022). The urgent need to cultivate individuals with strong character and resilience is evident in addressing these societal issues (Lapsley, 2025; Raman & Thomas, 2023; Thompson, 2014; Sharma & Singh, 2022). Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort to nurture well-rounded individuals, equipped with not only physical fitness, but also strong mental, moral and emotional foundations (Emde, 2016; Martone, 1998; Mata-McMahon et al., 2020; Tarsha & Narvaez, 2023; Narvaez et al., 2021; Thompson, 2014; Sharma & Singh, 2022). Understanding the intergenerational transmission of morality, values, and behaviors is crucial in shaping a healthier and more resilient society (Thompson, 2014; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Singh, 2022; Sharma et al., 2024a).

What if one could influence the development of a fetus' brain to ensure the birth of a well-cultured, intelligent, and talented child with exceptional qualities? Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) describe various techniques and cite numerous instances wherein by fostering a strong connection between mother and child, and prioritizing their physical, psychological, moral, and spiritual well-being even before the birth of the child, one could effectively plan for the arrival of a virtuous child (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Sharma, 2014; Sharma, 1972; Sharma & Singh, 2022; Sharma et al., 2024a; Dixit et al., 2025; Kulkarni and Kulkarni, nd). Several modern studies have also started realizing the importance of spirituality, virtues, and moral values in developing an emotionally sensitive and virtuous future generation (Martone, 1998; Tarsha & Narvaez, 2023; Narvaez et al., 2021; Thompson, 2014; Emde, 2016; Mata-McMahon et al., 2020; Bayne et al., 2023; Song et al., 2022; Sison and Redin, 2023; Chen et al., 2023; Domingo and Fernández Espinosa, 2025; Oldham and McLoughlin, 2025; Lapsley, 2025; Raman & Thomas, 2023).

Neuroscience accepts that repeated experiences shape neural pathways (Goldberg, 2022). IKS texts state that the good and bad activities of the child in his previous life are imprinted in his subconscious mind in the form of inherent impressions (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Sharma, 2014; Sharma, 1972; Sharma & Singh, 2022; Kulkarni and Kulkarni, nd). These texts recommend some subtle spiritual remedies that can affect the subtle level of human consciousness; these spiritual remedies are known as 'Sanskar', which literally means to refine, to rectify, to make beautiful, to make good and useful, to replace shortcomings of an object by establishing good qualities (virtues), to provide it a new shape (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Kulkarni and Kulkarni, nd; Dixit et al., 2025). Sanskar is an inherent tenet of one's personality that signifies refining, preserving, beautifying, and enhancing oneself; if the level of consciousness is improved, managed and uplifted through Sanskars, then the thoughts, character and behavior can be uplifted (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Sharma, 2014; Sharma, 1972; Sharma & Singh, 2022; Kulkarni and Kulkarni, nd; Dixit et al., 2025).

During the entire human life, there are sixteen Sanskars that are done at various important phases of life; three Sanskars are done before birth, and remaining are done after birth, i.e. naming (Namakaran), initiation of external food (Annaprashan), tonsure (Mundan), beginning of education (Vidyarambh), sacred thread ceremony (Yagyopaveet), marriage (Vivah), etc. (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b). By nurturing the consciousness through sixteen Sanskars, one can profoundly influence one's thoughts, character, and behavior, leading to all round personal development (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Singh, 2022; Kulkarni and Kulkarni, nd; Dixit et al., 2025). In this process, the introduction of newer Sanskars can influence existing ones, leading

to refinement or even elimination of old patterns (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Singh, 2022; Sharma et al., 2024a); in this regard, the responsibility lies on everyone - the parents, family, and the society at large.

Out of the sixteen Sanskars, the three that are done before birth are Garbhadhan (before pregnancy), Punsavan (at the third month of pregnancy) (Atharva Veda 6/19 (Sharma & Sharma, 2014); Ashvalayan Grihyasutra 1/13/1 (Sharma, 1972 - pg. 46)) and Seemantonayan (at the seventh month of pregnancy) (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b). Thus, these Sanskars are performed when the baby is inside the womb itself, i.e. when the foundation of gross, subtle and causal-bodies of the future child is laid down (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Singh, 2022).

Keeping in view the present challenges and circumstances of demanding modern life, the founder of All World Gayatri Pariwar, Pandit Shriram Sharma Acharya (Acharyashri), amalgamated the benefits, teachings, and scientific knowledge of these three Sanskars into a comprehensive program called 'Gharbhotsav Sanskar', which is done for inculcating good qualities in the unborn baby (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Singh, 2022). Gharbhotsav Sanskar is an IKS based technique that offers a pathway to shaping the fetus' brain, by inculcating virtuous tendencies and values in the mother and the baby through subtle treatment of the subconscious mind (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Singh, 2022; Sharma & Singh, 2023; Sharma & Singh, 2025; Sharma & Singh, 2026a; Sharma & Singh, 2026b; Sharma et al., 2024a; Sharma et al., 2024b). It is the psychological, social and spiritual teaching of reproductive science, and a celebration to make resolutions, in a supernatural sacred environment, in the presence of family members and friends, in a state of mind instilled with virtuous spiritual sentiments, through which, the attention of pregnant woman, the would-be father and other family members of the unborn is drawn towards the physical, mental, emotional, spiritual, virtuous development of the fetus (Dixit et al., 2025; Kulkarni and Kulkarni, nd; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Singh, 2022).

As per modern scientific understanding, maternal anxiety during pregnancy is a primary contributing factor in the development of preterm birth, while chronic stress and depression are significant underlying causes of low birth weight (Dunkel Schetter, 2011; Wadhwa et al., 1993; Wadhwa et al., 2011; Zhu et al., 2010; Mulligan et al., 2012; Tadanki et al., 2025). Elevated cortisol level constricts the vessels of the fetus, which in turn restricts the supply of oxygen and nutrients to the fetus; this may result in low birth weight, weak mental and emotional health, and may even cause less developed organs or various mental disorders after birth (Davis & Sandman, 2010; Mori & Shimosawa, 2025; Mustoe et al., 2012; Shriyan et al., 2023). High stress and cortisol levels in first-time mothers can affect fetal heart rate (Turan and Kaya, 2023). An increase in cortisol might even act as an early warning sign for an abnormally fast fetal heart rate (Turan and Kaya, 2023). Because of this, keeping the mother's stress levels low around the time of birth is essential for fetal well-being (Turan and Kaya, 2023). Therefore, knowledge about following a healthy and balanced daily routine, an ideal diet (balanced, Sattvic, Sanskarit (energized with virtuous feelings)), virtuous conduct, womb conversation, yogabhyas (yogic practices), and maintaining a healthy-spiritual environment for pregnant woman, is communicated, so that a virtuous, decent, and cultured future generation can be born (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Singh, 2022).

In this regard, continuous efforts have been made by Shantikunj, Haridwar, the headquarter of All World Gayatri Pariwar, under the "Aao Gadhe Sanskarvan Peedhi" movement (Sharma &

Singh, 2022; Sharma et al., 2024a). This movement involved three basic steps (Sharma & Singh, 2022; Sharma et al., 2024a). The first step was the organization of awareness camps throughout India; the number of such camps between 2019 to 2022 was in lakhs (Sharma & Singh, 2022; Sharma et al., 2024a). Simultaneously, trainer training sessions were also organized; and diligently, a nationwide network of grassroots volunteers was enrolled (Sharma & Singh, 2022; Sharma et al., 2024a).

In the second step, the trained volunteers contacted the pregnant women in their locality, conducted Garbhotsav Sanskar (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a) ceremonies, and provided continuous guidance and counseling throughout pregnancy, as well as after delivery (Sharma & Singh, 2022; Sharma & Singh, 2023; Sharma & Singh, 2025; Sharma & Singh, 2026a; Sharma & Singh, 2026b; Sharma et al., 2024a; Sharma et al., 2024b). They also collected data for research purpose for individual case studies; this data involved registration form for pregnant woman, informed consent form, participant information sheet, IKS based self-administered daily routine chart filled by the pregnant woman monthwise during entire pregnancy, a self-administered questionnaire filled by pregnant woman that captures her physical, mental, social and spiritual condition, both before starting the Garbhotsav Sanskar based intervention and the IKS based ideal daily routine, and after the completion of pregnancy (Sharma & Singh, 2022; Sharma & Singh, 2023; Sharma & Singh, 2025; Sharma & Singh, 2026a; Sharma & Singh, 2026b; Sharma et al., 2024a; Sharma et al., 2024b); three such case studies of pregnant women have been compiled so far, and the results are quite encouraging with regards to the physical, mental, social and spiritual benefits observed in the pregnant women (Sharma & Singh, 2023; Sharma et al., 2024b; Sharma & Singh, 2025; Sharma & Singh, 2026a).

The third step involved recording of the developmental milestones of the child (born after following the above IKS based intervention), wherein the mother was asked to fill a self-administered questionnaire, which gives the standard developmental milestones for a normal child, from birth up to 5 years, and is available from the website of the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (www.cdc.gov) (Zubler et al., 2022; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025a; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025b; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025c). The present paper depicts one such case study about the outcomes of the Garbhotsav Sanskar program for a pregnant woman, and her newborn child.

2. Methodology

In the present case study, the following action plan had been adopted by the 28 year old pregnant woman:

1. Registration form (Annexure-1) and consent form (Annexure-2) were filled by the pregnant woman (and co-signed by her family member). A participant information sheet (Annexure-3) was also given to the pregnant woman and signed by her (and co-signed by her family member). A trained regional volunteer made these forms available to her. These forms are generally filled on or before the third month of pregnancy.

2. Garbh Sanskar was performed by a volunteer. The method and teachings of Garbh Sanskar are given in the video (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a), and the books mentioned in the following references (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Sharma, 2015a; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b).

3. In the Sanskar ceremony, the pregnant woman, her husband, and other family members were made to take a pledge for the physical, mental, emotional, social, moral and spiritual development (health) of the pregnant woman and her unborn child (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Sharma, 2015a).

4. An ideal daily routine chart (see Annexure-4), based on the basic principles of Indian Knowledge Systems, was given to the pregnant woman, which was to be filled every month and given back to the volunteer.

5. Training was given on 5 topics, which have a positive impact on lifestyle – these topics are as follows:

i. Science and significance of Garbh Sanskar (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020b).

ii. Ideal daily routine (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2022a).

iii. Diet (balanced, sanskarit (pious, positively energized, virtuous) and sattvic (fresh pure vegetarian food)) (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2022c).

iv. Yogabhyas- Asana (Yogic postures), Pranayama and Dhyan (meditation) during pregnancy (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2022b).

v. Womb dialogue (Garbh Samvad) (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2025).

6. The pregnant woman was connected to the WhatsApp group of – “Maa ki Paathshala” (a type of online class for an ideal motherhood), so that she can stay in touch, and get continuous guidance. This group encourages to follow a regular ideal healthy routine, and guidance is given on the above topics. Sessions are conducted on different intellectual activities, Yog asanas, pranayama and meditation, etc. (books on this topic – Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 1998c; Sharma, 2015a; Sharma, 2008; Sharma, 2011; Sharma, 2015b; Sharma, 2010; Sharma, 2013; Sharma and Pandya, 2011; Sarsij, 2014).

7. A Questionnaire (see Annexure-5), developed in consultation with practicing Obstetricians and Gynaecologists, as well as experts of IKS, was used to record the input of the expectant mother about her overall health before and after adopting the ideal daily routine.

8. A Questionnaire (see Annexure-6) (Zubler et al., 2022; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025a; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025b; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025c) is used to record the input of the mother about the developmental milestones of the new-born child from birth till the age of 5 years (in the present case, the questionnaire from birth till the age of 2 years was given to the mother). It is noteworthy that the questionnaire given to the mother did not have the information about the months in which each milestone is supposed to be achieved by a normal child, as per the standard questionnaire (Zubler et al., 2022; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025a; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025b; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025c). This was done to mitigate any kind of bias in the information provided by the mother.

Expectant mother was asked to fill a ‘consent form’ (Annexure-2), which states that she agreed to participate in this research, agreed to fill questionnaires related to her overall health,

ideal daily routine, and her new-born child's physical and mental development, and also agreed that her data could be used for research purposes, publication and presentation after anonymization.

Some more details with regards to methodology are as follows.

2.1 Garbhotsav Sanskar Procedure

A brief outline of the procedure of Garbhotsav Sanskar (womb ceremony) is as follows (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b; Sharma, 2015a; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b).

(i) Pavitrikaranam (Purification): The ceremony starts by cleansing the expecting parents' minds and bodies. They sit quietly while water is sprinkled over them. The goal is to clear away any negative thoughts or emotions, creating a pure and positive environment for the baby growing inside.

(ii) Surya Dhyana-Pranayamah (Sun Meditation and Deep Meditative Breathing): The expecting mother practices deep breathing while focusing her thoughts on the sun. She imagines taking in the sun's life-giving energy. This practice is meant to build up the physical, mental, and spiritual strength of both herself and her baby.

(iii) Chandan Dharanam (Applying Sandalwood Paste / Tilak on the Forehead): A small mark of sandalwood paste is placed on the forehead. This is done to bring calmness to the mind, keep stressful emotions away, and help maintain clear, steady thinking.

(iv) Sankalpa, Kalash Pujan and Guru Vandana (Pledge and Divine Invocation): Everyone involved ties a holy thread (kalava - raksha sutra) around their wrists and promises to live by good moral values. Next, they pray to kalash (a water pot that represents the whole universe), and show reverence to their spiritual guide to ask for blessings and direction.

(v) Aushadhi Avaghrana (Herbal Inhalation and Consumption): The expecting mother breathes in and eats a special herbal powder made from Banyan, Giloy, and Peepal plants. Each plant has a special meaning: the Banyan stands for a long life, Giloy for good health and growth, and Peepal for high thinking and deep kindness.

(vi) Garbha Pujan and Ashwastana (Womb Worship and Assurance): The mother's womb is honored as a holy place where a divine soul is resting. The husband, the mother, and the rest of the family make a firm promise to keep the home peaceful, avoid arguments, and fully support the mother's food and emotional needs.

(vii) Charu Pradan (Offering Sweet Rice Pudding): The expecting mother eats a blessed bowl of sweet rice pudding, known as Kheer. The ingredients have special meanings: the rice stands for firmness and stability, the milk represents purity, and the sugar brings sweetness to life.

(viii) Agni Sthapan and Mantra Ahuti (Fire Ritual and Oblations with Mantras): Lamps are lit to represent the light of holy awareness. Then, offerings are placed into a sacred fire while chanting special prayers (the Gayatri and Mahamrityunjaya mantras). This is done to bless the baby with good physical, mental, and spiritual health.

(ix) Shanti Abhisinchanam and Visarjanam (Sprinkling Water for Peace and Bidding Farewell): The ritual ends by sprinkling blessed water over everyone to bring deep peace. Finally, the family thanks the divine beings for their presence and blessings, before respectfully seeing them off.

2.2 Promises of the Expecting Mother at the Time of 'Garbhotsav Sanskar' (Womb Ceremony)

To nurture an intelligent, well-cultured and healthy (physically, mentally, emotionally) baby, specific pledges are taken by the expecting mother during the Garbhotsav ceremony. By committing to follow these practices diligently throughout her pregnancy, she lays the foundation for a holistically developed virtuous child. These promises are (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b; Sharma, 2015a; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b):

- I will take good care of my body and make sure to stay active instead of being lazy.
- I will start my day with Atma-bodh (contemplating on the worthiness of life and firmly resolving to follow a virtuous routine during the entire day), followed by drinking three to four glasses of lukewarm or room-temperature water each morning.
- I will make it a daily habit to do light yoga, practice deep breathing (pranayama), and meditate.
- I will stick to a daily spiritual routine by praying sincerely, chanting mantras, and meditating upon the rising sun or another deity of my choice.
- I will regularly read the holy books of my religion, like the Ramayana, Bhagavad Gita, Bible, Quran, or Guru Granth Sahib.
- I will pay close attention to my lifestyle and diet, choosing only healthy, clean, and balanced vegetarian (sattvic) food.
- I will make daily spiritual offerings (such as Agnihotra or Balivaishwa Yagya) and eat my food as a blessing from God (Prasad). I will also listen to or sing calming, holy, inspirational music.
- I will develop a strong, loving bond with my baby by providing positive sound exposure daily for at least four hours. To nurture positive tenets in my child, I will listen to spiritual discourses, uplifting stories and calming, melodious music. I will also speak to my baby lovingly, tell virtuous stories, watch programs that impart constructive messages, practice meditation, and read aloud from inspirational books that focus on high human values and are authored by enlightened personalities.
- I will talk about good things and inspiring people, and I will keep myself happy by remembering the best and most joyful times of my life.
- I will make my home a happy and healthy place by putting up beautiful nature pictures, positive inspiring quotes, and photos of virtuous great personalities.
- I will be kind and friendly to everyone I meet, making sure to stay away from bad feelings like anger, jealousy, stubbornness, and bitterness.
- I will treat people with love and respect, helping to create a peaceful home where everyone works together and helps each other.
- I will put my energy into building a bright future for my baby, instead of wasting time complaining or holding onto grudges.
- I will read uplifting literature and biographies of noble personalities so that I can inculcate those virtuous fundamental human values in my child.
- I will stay completely away from scary, violent, or negative movies, television shows, and books. I will only watch and read things that are positive, uplifting and character building.

2.3 Promises to be Taken by Husband and Other Family Members

The husband and other family members take the following pledges during the Garbhotsav ceremony (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b; Sharma, 2015a; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b).

- Considering the unborn baby as a representative of God, we will welcome this divine soul by developing a home environment that is healthy, joyful, comfortable, and spiritually uplifting.
- Realizing that the womb is a sacred space, we will keep our home peaceful and completely avoid arguing, jealousy, hostility, or acting mean to one another.
- We will protect the child from bad influences. We will make sure the baby is never exposed to smoking, alcohol, bad behavior, or poverty.
- We promise to keep our home completely free from anger, stress, yelling, and fighting.
- We will provide the expecting mother with fresh, healthy and balanced vegetarian meals and health promoting drinks. We will treat her with immense respect and righteous conduct, and give her everything she needs to keep her mind relaxed and full of positive thoughts.
- We will lovingly fulfill the reasonable desires, aspirations and needs of the expecting mother with regards to behavior and food.

2.4 Guidelines for All-round Well-being

A set of guidelines given to the expecting mother and her family members, for her own and the unborn child's all-round well-being, are as follows (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b; Brahmavarchas, 1998b; Sharma & Singh, 2022).

2.4.1 Creating the Perfect Environment

To foster the perfect environment for the developing baby, an expecting mother is advised to adopt the following practices (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b):

- Keep a healthy daily routine: Plan out your day with good, healthy habits and make sure to stick to them.
- Exercise safely and breathe deeply: With your doctor's approval, do gentle yoga and breathing exercises. Pray, meditate, and chant holy words to help your baby grow strong and full of energy.
- Stay connected to your faith: Spend time reading the holy books of your religion, whether that is the Ramayana, Bhagavad Gita, Guru Granth Sahib, Bible, or Quran.
- Read positive books: Choose stories about brave, noble, honorable, and kind people. Stay completely away from anything that is scary, violent, or negative.
- Play soothing sounds for your baby: Listen to peaceful music and positive talks for about four hours a day, taking breaks as needed. This helps your baby's mind grow.
- Create a happy space: Make your home joyful by remembering good times, enjoying nature, and decorating your rooms with beautiful pictures and uplifting quotes.
- Eat clean, healthy food: Nourish your body with fresh, home-cooked vegetarian meals. Avoid eating food that is old, extremely spicy, or deep-fried.
- Focus on good feelings: Work hard to let go of anger, jealousy, and sadness. Instead, try to be as kind, caring, and giving as possible.
- Choose your entertainment carefully: Protect your mind by avoiding sad, stressful, or

overly intense movies, television shows, and conversations.

- Build a peaceful home: Create a loving family environment where everyone respects each other, cares for one another, and works together without fighting.

2.4.2 Disciplines for Positive Support (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

- Rise early: Waking up early, especially before the sun rises, is great for your body and mind. It provides the quietest and best time to meditate.
- Hydrate first thing: Drink about three glasses of plain or lukewarm water right after waking up, before eating anything. This easy habit cleans your blood, helps digest your food, and keeps your stomach working smoothly.
- Engage in morning movement: After brushing your teeth and washing up, set aside time to do your safe yoga stretches and deep breathing exercises.
- Chant sacred mantras: While you meditate, silently repeat powerful holy prayers in your mind, such as the Gayatri Mantra or the Mahamrityunjaya Mantra.
- Nourish yourself consistently: Always eat breakfast. For the rest of the day, fuel your body with healthy, balanced, and small meals spaced out evenly.
- Prioritize adequate rest: Make sure to get a good six to seven hours of sleep every night. Also, give yourself one to two hours during the day to just relax, which can include a short 20-minute nap.
- Reflect before bed: End your day by reading positive, inspiring books. Take a few quiet moments to think about your actions that day, figure out how you can do better, and focus on personal growth.
- Embrace your divine role: Keep reminding yourself that your baby is a special gift given to your care. Be thankful for this beautiful chance to raise a wonderful person who will bring pride and happiness to your family and the world.

2.5 Beneficial Exercises for Pregnancy

Medical professionals make strong recommendations for incorporating simple and gentle exercises into your routine for the minimization of any kind of discomfort and preparing your body for a smooth delivery.

Note: You should strictly avoid exercising if any kind of complications are experienced such as premature rupture of membranes, high blood pressure, a low-lying placenta, bleeding, heart disease, restricted fetal growth.

Here are some commonly recommended exercises for expecting mothers (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b):

- Morning Walks: Go for an easy, slow walk outside in the morning while taking deep breaths. This is a great way to start moving your body.
- Gentle Joint Circles: Lie down and slowly spin your left foot in circles, going both ways. Do the exact same thing with your right foot. You can also do these slow circles to loosen up your wrists, shoulders, and neck.
- Kegels (Pelvic Floor Exercises): Lie on the back and bend the knees; bring the feet close to the hips. Gently tighten and contract the perineum muscles. Regularly practice pelvic floor exercises to build flexibility and strength in your perineal muscles. This important practice helps in carrying the extra weight of the baby, prevents leakage of urine, prepares the body for a smoother delivery, and enhances the speed of postpartum recovery.
- Cat Pose: Get on your hands and knees with a flat back. Slowly pull your abdominal

muscles inward toward your spine, drop your head down, hold for 15 seconds, and then relax.

- Squats and Butterfly Pose: Squats: Stand with your feet wide apart and slowly bend your knees to lower your bottom toward the floor. Butterfly Pose: Sit on the floor, press the bottoms of your feet together in front of you, and let your knees drop down to the sides.
- Back and Leg Extensions: Get down on your hands and knees. Slowly lift and stretch your left arm forward and simultaneously extend your right leg straight back.
- Bridge Pose: Lie on your back and pull your feet close to your bottom. Push your feet into the floor to lift your hips up into the air, then slowly lower them back down.
- Half Chair Pose: Stand with your feet a little bit apart. Reach your arms straight out in front of you, bend your knees just a little bit (like you are about to sit in a tall chair), and stay in that position for 15 to 20 seconds.
- Resting Pose: Lie flat on your back with your legs slightly apart. Lay your arms next to your sides with your hands facing up. Stay totally still and just pay attention to your breathing.

2.5.1 Ideal Body Postures During Pregnancy (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

- Stand tall but stay relaxed: Stand up straight, but let your shoulders drop down naturally. Your body should feel comfortable, not stiff or strained.
- Use back support when sitting: Whenever you take a seat, sit up straight and make sure your back is resting firmly against the chair or a good pillow.
- Sit on the floor for your belly: To help keep your stomach muscles strong, try sitting flat on the floor with your legs straight out in front of you. Lean back just a little bit and use your hands to prop yourself up.
- Bend your knees to lift things: When you pick something up off the floor, always squat down by bending your knees. Never bend over at the waist, to protect your back from getting hurt.
- Squeeze your lower muscles: Lie flat on your back with your knees bent. Practice squeezing and then letting go of the muscles in your perineum to help them get stronger.
- Sleep on your left side: Try to always sleep on your left side. This helps blood move better through your body and to your baby. For extra comfort, put a soft pillow between your legs.

2.5.2 Breathing Exercises (Pranayama) for Expecting Mother (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

During pregnancy, maintaining a healthy respiratory system is extremely important, as the growing baby completely relies on you for oxygen. The practice of regular breathing exercises (Pranayama) helps in meeting this increased oxygen demand, while offering immense physical relief and mental peace. Consistent practice of these techniques can even help in the management of labor pain; thus, these practices are as important in your routine as proper medical care and a nutritious diet.

Recommended Pranayama Techniques (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b):

- Deep Breathing: Sit in a comfortable posture on the floor, keeping the spine straight, hands on your lap or on the ground. Take a slow, deep breath in; draw as much air into your lungs as possible while visualizing that pious, divine energy is being filled in

your body. Gently and fully exhale, pushing all the air out.

- Anulom-Vilom (Alternate Nostril Breathing): Gently close your right nostril with your thumb and do deep inhalation through the left nostril. Next, use the little finger to close the left nostril, and release your thumb in order to exhale slowly from the right nostril. Now, inhale through the right nostril, close it with your thumb, and exhale through the left.
- Pranakarsan Pranayam (Energy-Drawing Breath): Begin by slowly breathing out all the air that is currently in your lungs. Through both the nostrils take a deep, slow breath in, and fill your lungs up to their maximum capacity; all the while imagine that vital life energy and positive thoughts are being absorbed by you. Next, exhale fully, and visualize that you are releasing all physical tension, negativity, and ailments, from your body and mind.
- Bhramari Pranayam (Humming Bee Breath): Sit straight in a comfortable cross-legged position or on a chair. Gently close your eyes and lips; ensure your teeth are kept slightly apart instead of being clenched. With the help of your index fingers gently close your ears. Take a deep breath in, and while you are slowly exhaling through your nose, make a steady, soothing humming sound that is similar to that of a buzzing bee.
- Ujjayi Pranayama: Keep your mouth closed. Gently constrict the back of your throat. Inhale slowly and deeply through both nostrils. You should hear a soft, continuous hissing or rushing sound internally. Pull the breath deep into your lower belly, then expand your ribcage, and finally fill your upper chest. Maintain the same gentle constriction in the throat. Exhale slowly and steadily through both nostrils. The exhalation should make the same soothing sound as the inhalation. Try to make your inhalations and exhalations equal in length and smooth in texture. There should be no jerking or pausing in the breath.

2.5.3 Devout Meditation (Dhyan Yog) for Expecting Mothers (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

- Embrace the purpose: Devout meditation aims at focusing your mind in order to establish a deep, meaningful connection with the divine, i.e. a supreme spiritual power.
- Find a peaceful sanctuary: Pick a calm, comfortable spot outside in the fresh air where no one will bother you.
- Breathe and chant: Breathe slowly and simultaneously chant the Gayatri Mantra either mentally or softly; this helps to purify and focus your thoughts.
- Inhale positivity: As you take a deep breath in, imagine that pure vital energy, noble qualities, and positive reflections are entering your body and flowing to the fetus (baby in the womb).
- Exhale negativity: When breathing out, visualize that all the vices, stress, and negative instincts are being discarded, and your mind is becoming completely cleansed, calm, and peaceful.

2.6 Nurturing the Mental Health of Your Baby in the Womb (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

- Understand how stress hurts: Experts say many babies are born already feeling stressed out. This can cause them to have behavior problems and struggle as they grow up.
- Protect your growing baby: A very stressful home can harm the baby inside you. It can stop both their body and their brain from growing the way they should.

- Work together for a calm home: It is up to both the mother and her whole family to keep the house peaceful, loving, and quiet. This teamwork helps make sure the baby is born healthy.
- Look inward and read good books: Lower your stress by taking time to think quietly about your actions and how to grow as a person. Reading virtuous books that make you feel happy and inspired also helps.
- Spend time with good people: Hang out with kind, wise people and listen to uplifting spiritual talks. This will clear your mind and help you let go of your worries.
- Read uplifting stories: Choose books that give you hope and fill your mind with good thoughts. Read stories about brave, kind, and generous heroes from history.

2.7 Essential Precautions for Your Daily Routine (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

- Do not lift heavy things: Keep your body safe and avoid straining yourself by not picking up or carrying heavy items.
- Stay calm and happy: Protect your peace by trying your best to avoid feeling scared, stressed out, or angry.
- Always ask your doctor about medicine: Never take any pills, even basic ones you buy off the shelf at the store, without checking with your doctor first.
- Avoid loud noises: Stay away from loud, harsh noises and blasting music. Keep the sounds around you soft and quiet for your baby.
- Say no to bad habits and limit caffeine: Do not smoke, drink alcohol, or use any drugs. Also, make sure you do not drink too much coffee or tea.
- Use your time well: Stay active doing useful things. Try not to be lazy, pick up bad habits, or waste time gossiping about other people.
- Limit screen time: Spend less time on your phone, watching television, surfing the internet, and using social media to cut down on radiation from electronics.

2.8 Specific Meal Plans and Recipes (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

2.8.1 Daily Refreshments and Recipes (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

- Early Morning Snack (5:00 AM): Start your day with either two spoonfuls of sattu (roasted grain powder), OR a small mix of five almonds, two walnuts, and two dried dates.
- Night-time Drink (8:00 PM): Before bed, enjoy a soothing glass of milk mixed with a tiny bit of turmeric and some honey.
- Healthy Mixed Flour: Make a nutritious flour at home by combining 7 kilograms of wheat, 1 kilogram of chickpeas, 1 kilogram of soybeans, and 1 kilogram of barley. You can also add other whole grains like millet. Just remember to soak, dry, roast, and peel the soybeans before mixing them in.
- Making Sattu Powder: To make your own sattu, simply clean, dry-roast, and grind up a mixture of barley, chickpeas, and soybeans into a fine powder.
- Sprouts Recipe: Make a healthy sprout mix by putting together a small handful of peanuts (10 grams), some black chickpeas (15 grams), and whole green lentils (25 grams).

2.8.2 Seven-Day Meal Plan (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

The proposed 7-day meal plan for a pregnant woman is given in Table 1. The standard meal timings are Breakfast at 8:00 AM, Lunch at 11:00 AM - 12:00 PM, Evening Break at 3:00 PM, and Dinner at 6:00 PM. One can take fruits and juices in between.

Table 1. The proposed 7-day meal plan for a pregnant woman (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b).

Day	Breakfast (8:00AM)	Lunch (11:00AM - 12:00PM)	Evening Break (3:00PM)	Dinner (6:00PM)
Day 1	1 Banana / Any Fruit / 1 bowl Vegetable Oatmeal + 250g Yogurt	2 Roti + 1 cup Rice + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 cup Arhar Daal + 3/4 cup Yogurt	1 Fruit / 1/2 cup Sprout / 1/2 cup Fried Gram / 1 cup Veg Soup / 1 glass Buttermilk	2 Roti + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 cup Green Moong Daal + 1 Chhena Sweet
Day 2	Any Fruit + 250g Yogurt / 1 Banana / 1 cup Idli or Poha / Dhokla + Coconut Sauce	2 Roti + 1 cup Rice + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 cup Rajma Daal + 3/4 cup Yogurt	1 Fruit / 1½ cup Sprout / 1 cup Puffed Wheat / 1 cup Roasted Soybean / 1 glass Buttermilk	2 Roti + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 cup Arhar Daal + 1 cup Kheer
Day 3	Paneer-Stuffed Roti / 1 Banana / Any Fruit + 250g Yogurt or Milk	2 Roti + 1 cup Rice + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 cup Moong Daal + 3/4 cup Yogurt	1 Fruit / Green Salad / 1 cup Popcorn / 1 glass Buttermilk	1.5 cup Veg Oatmeal + 1 Chhena Sweet
Day 4	Vegetable Upma / 1 cup Sprouts / 1 Banana / Any Fruit + 250g Yogurt or Milk	2 Roti + 1 cup Rice + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 cup Masoor Daal + 3/4 cup Yogurt	1 Fruit / 1 cup Sprout / 1 cup Roasted Rice & Gram / 1 glass Buttermilk	2 Roti + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 cup Lobiya (Rasedar) + 1 cup Kheer

Day 5	1 cup Fruit Salad / 1 Stuffed Paneer Roti + 1 cup Yogurt	2 Roti + 1 cup Rice + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 cup Lobiya (Rasedar) + 3/4 cup Yogurt	1 Fruit / 1/2 cup Sprout / 1 cup Puffed Wheat / 1 glass Buttermilk	2 Roti + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 cup Moong Daal + Sweet Dish
Day 6	1 cup Poha / 1 Stuffed Paratha + 250g Yogurt or Milk	2 Roti + 1 cup Rice + Green Veg + Paneer (Rasedar) + 3/4 cup Yogurt	1 Fruit / 1/2 cup Sprout / 1 cup Popcorn / 1 glass Buttermilk	1 Stuffed Roti + 1 cup Green Veg + 1 Chhena Sweet
Day 7	Dhokla + Coconut Sauce / 1 Banana / Any Fruit + 250g Yogurt or Milk	4 Poori + 1 cup Green Veg / 1 cup Chhola Dal + 3/4 cup Yogurt	1 Fruit / 1 cup Roasted Gram / 1 glass Buttermilk	Tomato Soup / Veg Khichari + Sweet Kheer

2.8.3 *Additional Dietary Notes* (Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2019; Brahmavarchas, 2016b)

- Drink plenty of water: Make sure to drink about 8 to 10 glasses (2 liters) of water every day. However, try to avoid drinking water right while you are eating. Instead, wait for an hour or an hour and a half after your meal to drink a good amount of water.
- Eat fresh coconut: If you can, try to eat a quarter of a fresh coconut each day as a healthy snack.

3. Results

In the present individual case study, the pregnant woman (age 28 years, from Haryana) was registered for Maa-ki-pathshala. She followed the prescribed ideal daily routine (Annexure-4) to the maximum extent possible.

Through a questionnaire (Annexure-5), questions were asked about her overall health status, before and after following the ideal daily routine. The answers of the pregnant woman are given in Table 2, and illustrated in Figures 1 to 4. As can be seen from Table 2, and Figures 1 to 4, positive/constructive/healthy changes were observed in the daily routine of the pregnant woman, with regards to performing daily morning activities such as Atma-bodh (contemplating on the worthiness of life and firmly resolving to follow a virtuous routine during the entire day), drinking 3 glasses of water (Usha-paan), bathing, defecation, etc. and other household chores with music; taking meals with music/mantra; regularity in going for evening walk; Tatva-bodh (analyzing the day's work and resolving for self-analysis, self-correction, self-improvement and self-development) and listening to prayer/music/mantra before going to bed, etc. Apart from this, there are some other activities such as doing yog asanas with music, doing pranayama, dhyān (meditation); doing womb dialogue with

different techniques like inspirational songs (Pragya Geet), telling stories, chanting mantras, listening to talks that promote positivity, playing mindful games, practicing good hobbies, etc., which were not generally a part of her earlier daily routine; she started to perform the above activities quite regularly, after gaining knowledge about these. The adoption and regularity of these practices led to various kinds of improvements in her overall health, such as - earlier she used to catch cough and cold sometimes, but after following the ideal daily routine this situation improved; earlier she used to sometimes feel tired and lack of energy, but after following the ideal daily routine this almost stopped occurring.

Table 2: Answers given by the pregnant woman to the questions that were asked to her about her overall health status (physical, mental, spiritual health, and familial/social relation), before and after following the ideal daily routine. Positive/constructive/healthy changes were observed in response to most of the questions.

S. No.	Physical health before/after following the ideal routine	Before following Ideal routine			After following Ideal routine		
		Yes	Sometime	No	Yes	Sometime	No
1.	Did/Do you feel hungry at the proper (good appetite) time?		Sometime		Yes		
2.	Did/ Do you drink 8 to 9 glasses of water?			No	Yes		
3.	Did/Do you drink water in the early morning or before sunrise regularly?			No	Yes		
4.	Did/Do you take a light breakfast?			No	Yes		
5.	Did/Do you eat sprouts regularly?	Yes			Yes		
6.	Did/do you consume multi-colored fruits and vegetables?		Sometime		Yes		
7.	Did/Do you take any intoxication?			No			No
8.	Did/Do you walk in the morning/evening regularly?			No	Yes		
9.	Did/Do you do yogasan regularly?			No	Yes		
10.	Were/Are you able to climb stairs comfortably?	Yes			Yes		
11.	Were/Are you able to do household chores that require less physical energy such as cooking, dusting, folding clothes, etc.?	Yes			Yes		
12.	Were/Are you able to do household chores that require extensive physical energy such as brooming, mopping, washing clothes by hand, etc.?	Yes			Yes		
13.	Did/Do you catch cold and fever frequently?		Sometime				No
14.	Did/Do you feel vomiting?			No		Sometime	
15.	Did/Do you wash your hands before taking meal?	Yes			Yes		
16.	Did/Do you maintain personal hygiene such as bathing regularly, brushing your teeth before sleep, etc.?	Yes			Yes		
17.	Did/Do you maintain the hygiene and cleanliness of the kitchen, toilets, drains, dustbin, etc.?	Yes			Yes		
18.	Did/Do you wake up before sunrise?		Sometime		Yes		
19.	Did/Do you make the schedule for the coming day in the morning?			No	Yes		

20	Did/ Do you do pranayama along with womb conversation?			No	Yes		
21	Did/Do you take an afternoon nap?		Sometime				No
22	Did/Do you take snacks at noon?		Sometime		Yes		
23	Did/Do you take a light meal at night?	Yes			Yes		
24	Do you walk in the evening?		Sometime		Yes		
25	Did/Do you add turmeric and honey to milk before consuming it?			No	Yes		
26	Did/Do you consume non-vegetarian food?			No			No
27	Did/do you still use mobile, laptop, electronic gadgets, or any other digital electronics?	Yes					No
28	Was/Is someone consuming cigarettes, tobacco, alcohol or any other intoxication in your family.			No			No
29	Did/Do you do yogasana with soothing music?			No	Yes		

S. No.	Mental health before/after following the ideal routine	Before following Ideal routine			After following Ideal routine		
		Yes	Sometime	No	Yes	Sometime	No
1.	Did/Do you face any problems in daily household management?		Sometime				No
2.	Did/Do you have any problem related to sleep?			No			No
3.	Did/Do you feel tired and lack of energy?		Sometime				No
4.	Did/Do gloomy and depressed states persist?		Sometime				No
6.	Were/Are you satisfied?						
	1. From your health			No	Yes		
	2. From your relations	Yes			Yes		
7.	Were/Are you feel happy?		Sometime		Yes		
8.	Did/Do you listen spiritual discourses / sermons and do womb conversation?			No	Yes		
9.	I was/am a calm and balanced person.			No	Yes		
10.	Did/Do you do Swadhyaya (Reading enlightening and inspirational books and contemplating on them)?			No	Yes		
11.	Did/Do you meditate along with womb conversation?			No	Yes		

S. No.	Social and familial relations before/after following the ideal routine	Before following Ideal routine			After following Ideal routine		
		Yes	Sometime	No	Yes	Sometime	No
1.	Was/Is there harmony between you and your husband?	Yes			Yes		
2.	Was/Is there harmony between you and your family?	Yes			Yes		
3.	Were /Are you surrounded by people whom you can trust?	Yes					No
4.	Were/Are you capable of solving the problems through conversations?				Yes		
5.	Did/Do you have at least one friend whom you can trust?	Yes			Yes		
6.	Did/Do you make the environment abusive, offensive, quarrelsome and depressed.		Sometime				No

7.	Did/Do you talk to your unborn child?		Sometime		Yes		
8.	Did/Do your family members talk to the unborn child?			No		Sometime	
9.	Did/Do you support and help your family members?	Yes			Yes		
10.	Did/Do you help and support your neighbors in their grief?	Yes			Yes		
11.	Did/Do you donate a part of your income for the welfare and upliftment of society?	Yes			Yes		
12.	Did/Do you donate some time for the welfare of society?			No	Yes		
13.	Did/Do your family members help you with your household chores?	Yes			Yes		
14.	In times of crisis, would/will your family provide the support and help that you needed/need?	Yes			Yes		
15.	In times of crisis, would/will your friend provide the support and help that you needed/need?	Yes			Yes		
16.	In times of crisis, would/will your neighbors provide the support and help that you needed/need?		Sometime		Yes		
17.	Did/Do all the family members perform worship (arti and pooja), swadhyaya (Reading enlightening and inspirational books and contemplating on them) and dinner together in the evening?		Sometime		Yes		
18.	Did/Do you do Balivaishv Yagya (Sacrament to offer a small part of cooked meal to sacred fire before taking meal)	Yes			Yes		

S. No.	Spiritual health before/after following the ideal routine	Before following Ideal routine			After following Ideal routine		
		Yes	Sometime	No	Yes	Sometime	No
1.	Did/Do you do analysis of your good-bad deeds and thoughts, performed in the entire day, before going to bed			No	Yes		
2.	Did/Do you, immediately after waking up, consider the coming day as life for one day, and plan the day ahead for its proper and ideal utilization?			No	Yes		
3.	Did/Do you recite the Gayatri Mantra or any other mantra regularly?		Sometime		Yes		
4.	Did/Do you do introspection (Chintan-self-analysis and self- correction, Manan self-improvement, self-development)?			No	Yes		
5.	Did/Do you perform yagya (sacrament to offer the oblation in the scared fire) regularly?		Sometime		Yes		
6.	Did/Do you do swadhyaya (reading enlightening and inspirational books and contemplating on them)?		Sometime		Yes		
7.	Did/Do you feel satisfied by closeness to God?			No	Yes		
8.	Did/Do you think that you were born for some great objective?			No	Yes		
9.	Did/Do you believe that God is with you in times of crisis?				Yes		

10.	I enjoyed/enjoy my life.	Yes			Yes		
11.	God loved/loves us and He protected/protects us.	Yes			Yes		
12.	Did/Do you agree that the baby developing in your womb is the representative of the Almighty?	Yes			Yes		
13.	Did/Do you perform aarti (singing hymns praising the Almighty) regularly?		Sometime		Yes		
14.	Did/Do you energize your food through mantras and prayers while cooking, serving and before consuming it?		Sometime		Yes		
15.	Do you meditate on light as a reflection of your own self?			No	Yes		
16.	Were/Are you satisfied from your life?			No	Yes		

Figure 1. Questions asked to the pregnant woman about her physical health before and after following the ideal daily routine, as well as the answers given by her. The Y-axis has the question numbers; the corresponding questions are listed on the right side of the graph. The X-axis has values - 0 meaning No; 0.5 meaning Sometimes; 1 meaning Yes. The light green bar depicts the answer before following the ideal routine. The dark pink bar depicts the answer after following the ideal routine.

Mental Health of the Pregnant Woman

Figure 2. Questions asked to the pregnant woman about her mental health before and after following the ideal daily routine, as well as the answers given by her. The Y-axis has the question numbers; the corresponding questions are listed on the right side of the graph. The X-axis has values - 0 meaning No; 0.5 meaning Sometimes; 1 meaning Yes. The light green bar depicts the answer before following the ideal routine. The dark pink bar depicts the answer after following the ideal routine.

Figure 3. Questions asked to the pregnant woman about her spiritual health before and after following the ideal daily routine, as well as the answers given by her. The Y-axis has the question numbers; the corresponding questions are listed on the right side of the graph. The X-axis has values - 0 meaning No; 0.5 meaning Sometimes; 1 meaning Yes. The light green bar depicts the answer before following the ideal routine. The dark pink bar depicts the answer after following the ideal routine.

Figure 4. Questions asked to the pregnant woman about her familial/social relation before and after following the ideal daily routine, as well as the answers given by her. The Y-axis has the question numbers; the corresponding questions are listed on the right side of the graph. The X-axis has values - 0 meaning No; 0.5 meaning Sometimes; 1 meaning Yes. The light green bar depicts the answer before following the ideal routine. The dark pink bar depicts the answer after following the ideal routine.

Through another Questionnaire (see Annexure-6), questions were asked to the mother about the developmental milestones of the new-born child from birth till the age of 2 years. It is noteworthy that this questionnaire (Annexure-6) did not have the information about the months, as per the standard questionnaire (Zubler et al., 2022; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025a; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025b; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025c), in which each milestone is supposed to be achieved by a normal child. This was done to mitigate any kind of bias in the information provided by the mother. The answers of the mother about the developmental milestones of the new-born child from birth till the age of 2 years are given in Table 3 and Figures 5 to 8. As can be seen in Table 3 and Figures 5 to 8, the first column has the months in which each developmental milestone is achieved by a normal child; the second column has the Social/Emotional Milestones, Language/Communication Milestones, Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving), and Movement/Physical Development Milestones for a normal child corresponding to the months given in column 1; the third column has the milestones given in Hindi language; the fourth column has the information provided by the mother regarding the months in which each milestone was achieved by the new-born child.

It can be seen from Table 3 and Figures 5 to 8 that more than 90% of the milestones had been achieved by the new-born child earlier than those expected for a normal child. Furthermore, it is especially noteworthy from Table 3 and Figures 5 to 8 that all the milestones from 12 months up to 2 years had been achieved by the new-born child in less than or equal to 12 months.

Table 3: Questionnaire - Questions that were asked to the mother about the developmental milestones of her new-born child from birth till the age of 2 years (Zubler et al., 2022; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025a; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025b; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025c). The answers of the mother are also given therein.

उम्र (महीने) Age (Months) as per scale	Activity	गतिविधि	गर्भोत्सव बच्चे की उम्र (दिन/महीने) Garbhotsav Child's age (Days/Months)
As per standard scale	Social/Emotional Milestones	सामाजिक/भावनात्मक उपलब्धियाँ	
by 2 months	Calms down when spoken to or picked up	बात करने या उठाए जाने पर शांत हो जाते हैं	1 Month
by 2 months	Looks at your face	आपका चेहरा देखता है	2 Month
by 2 months	Seems happy to see you when you walk up to her	जब आप उसके पास जाते हैं तो आपको देखकर खुश होता है	3 Month
by 2 months	Smiles when you talk to or smile at her	जब आप उससे बात करते हैं या मुस्कराते हैं तो वह मुस्कराता है	2 Month
	Language/Communication Milestones	भाषा/संचार संबंधी उपलब्धियाँ	
by 2 months	Makes sounds other than crying	रौने के अलावा और भी आवाज़ें निकालता है	2 ½ Month
by 2 months	Reacts to loud sounds	तेज आवाज़ पर प्रतिक्रिया देता है	1 Month
	Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving)	संज्ञानात्मक उपलब्धियाँ (सीखना, सोचना, समस्या-समाधान)	
by 2 months	Watches you as you move	जब आप गतिविधि करते हैं तो आपको देखता है	2 ½ Month
by 2 months	Looks at a toy for several seconds	खिलौने को कुछ सेकंड के लिए देखता है	2 ½ Month
	Movement/Physical Development Milestones	गतिविधि / शारीरिक विकास की उपलब्धियाँ	
by 2 months	Holds head up when on tummy	पेट के बल लेटने पर सिर ऊपर करता है	1 ½ Month
by 2 months	Moves both arms and both legs	दोनों हाथों और दोनों पैरों को हिलाता है	15 day
by 2 months	Opens hands briefly	संक्षेप में हाथ खोलता है	1 Month
	Social/Emotional Milestones	सामाजिक/भावनात्मक उपलब्धियाँ	
by 4 months	Smiles on his own to get your attention	आपका ध्यान आकर्षित करने के लिए खुद मुस्कराता है	2 ½ Month
by 4 months	Chuckles (not yet a full laugh) when you try to make her laugh	जब आप उसे हँसाने की कोशिश करते हैं तो हँसता है (अभी तक पूरी हँसी नहीं)	2 Month

by 4 months	Looks at you, moves, or makes sounds to get or keep your attention	आपका ध्यान आकर्षित करने या बनाए रखने के लिए आपकी ओर देखता है, हिलता-डुलता है या आवाज करता है	2 ½ Month
	Language/Communication Milestones	भाषा/संचार संबंधी उपलब्धियाँ	
by 4 months	Makes sounds like “oooo”, “aahh” (cooing)	"ऊ", "आह" (गुटरगू करना) जैसी आवाज़ें निकालता है	2 ½ Month
by 4 months	Makes sounds back when you talk to him	जब आप उससे बात करते हैं तो आवाज़ करके प्रतिक्रिया देता है	3 Month
by 4 months	Turns head towards the sound of your voice	आपकी आवाज़ की ओर सिर घमाता है	2 ½ Month
	Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving)	संज्ञानात्मक उपलब्धियाँ (सीखना, सोचना, समस्या-समाधान)	
by 4 months	If hungry, opens mouth when she sees breast or bottle	भूख लगे तो स्तन या बोतल देखकर मुँह खोलता है	2 Month
by 4 months	Looks at his hands with interest	अपने हाथों को दिलचस्पी से देखता है	3 Month
	Movement/Physical Development Milestones	गतिविधि / शारीरिक विकास की उपलब्धियाँ	
by 4 months	Holds head steady without support when you are holding her	जब आप उसे गोद में लिए हुए हों तो सिर को बिना सहारे के स्थिर रखता है	2 ½ Month
by 4 months	Holds a toy with both hand (bidexterous) when you put it in his hand	जब आप उसके हाथ में एक खिलौना रखते हैं तो उसे पकड़ता है	3Month
by 4 months	Uses her arm to swing at toys	खिलौनों को घुमाने के लिए अपने हाथ का उपयोग करता है	6 Month
by 4 months	Brings hands to mouth	मुँह में हाथ डालता है	
by 4 months	Pushes up onto elbows/forearms when on tummy	जब पेट के बल लेटा हो तो कोहनियों/कलाईयों के बल खुद को उठाता है	3 Month
	Social/Emotional Milestones	सामाजिक/भावनात्मक उपलब्धियाँ	
by 6 months	Knows familiar people	परिचित लोगों को जानता है	3 Month
by 6 months	Likes to look at himself in a mirror	खुद को आईने में देखना पसंद करता है	3 Month
by 6 months	Laughs	हँसता है	2 Month
	Language/Communication Milestones	भाषा/संचार संबंधी उपलब्धियाँ	
by 6 months	Takes turns making sounds with you	आपके साथ-साथ आवाज़ें निकालता है बा, पा, गा (mono syllable)	4 Month
by 6 months	Blows “raspberries” (sticks tongue out and blows)	"कुलबुलाहट" जैसी आवाज़ें निकालता है (जोभ बाहर निकालकर होंठों में दबाकर जोर से हवा निकालना)	4 Month
by 6 months	Makes squealing noises	कर्कश आवाज़ें निकालता है	4 Month

	Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving)	संज्ञानात्मक उपलब्धियाँ (सीखना, सोचना, समस्या-समाधान)	
by 6 months	Puts things in her mouth to explore them	चीजों के बारे में जानने के लिए अपने मुँह में डालती है	5 Month
by 6 months	Reaches to grab a toy he wants	जो उसे चाहिए उस खिलौने को लेने के लिए पहुँचता है	7 Month
by 6 months	Closes lips to show she doesn't want more food	यह दिखाने के लिए होंठ बंद करता है कि उसे और खाना नहीं चाहिए	7 Month
	Movement/Physical Development Milestones	गतिविधि / शारीरिक विकास की उपलब्धियाँ	
by 6 months	Rolls from tummy to back	पेट से पीठ तक रोल करता है	5 Month
by 6 months	Pushes up with straight arms when on tummy	पेट के बल सीधे हाथों से ऊपर उठता है	5 Month
by 6 months	Leans on hands to support himself when sitting)	बैठने पर खुद को सहारा देने के लिए हाथों पर झुक जाता है	5 Month
	Social/Emotional Milestones	सामाजिक/भावनात्मक उपलब्धियाँ	4-6 Month
by 9 months	Is shy, clingy, or fearful around strangers	अजनबियों के आसपास शर्मीला है, चिपक जाता है या भयभीत होता है	5 Month
by 9 months	Shows several facial expressions, like happy, sad, angry, and surprised	चेहरे के कई भाव दिखाता है, जैसे खुश, उदास, क्रोधित, और आश्चर्यचकित	4 Month
by 9 months	Looks when you call her name	जब आप उसका नाम पुकारते हैं तो देखता है	4 Month
by 9 months	Reacts when you leave (looks, reaches for you, or cries)	जब आप बाहर जाते हैं तो प्रतिक्रिया देता है (देखता है, आपकी ओर बाँहें फैलाता है या रोता है)	6 Month
by 9 months	Smiles or laughs when you play peek-a-boo	जब आप छिपकर उसकी ओर देखने का खेल खेलते हैं तो मुस्कराता या हँसता है	5 Month
	Language/Communication Milestones	भाषा/संचार संबंधी उपलब्धियाँ	
by 9 months	Makes different sounds like "mamamama" and "babababa"	"मामामामा" और "बाबाबाबा" जैसी अलग-अलग आवाज़ें निकालता है	5 Month
by 9 months	Lifts arms up to be picked up	उठाए जाने के लिए हाथ ऊपर करता है	5 Month
	Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving)	संज्ञानात्मक उपलब्धियाँ (सीखना, सोचना, समस्या-समाधान)	
by 9 months	Looks for objects when dropped out of sight (like his spoon or toy)	दृष्टि से दूर होने पर वस्तुओं की तलाश करता है (जैसे उसका चम्मच या खिलौना)	8 Month
by 9 months	Bangs two things together	दो चीजों को आपस में टकराता है	7 Month
	Movement/Physical Development Milestones	गतिविधि / शारीरिक विकास की उपलब्धियाँ	
by 9 months	Gets to a sitting position by herself	अपने आप बैठ जाता है	7 Month
by 9 months	Moves things from one hand to her other hand	चीजों को एक हाथ से दूसरे हाथ में ले जाता है	7 Month
by 9 months	Uses fingers to "rake" food towards himself	भोजन को अपनी ओर खींचकर लाने के लिए उंगलियों का उपयोग करता है	7 Month

by 9 months	Sits without support	बिना सहारे के बैठता है	6 Month
	Social/Emotional Milestones	सामाजिक/भावनात्मक उपलब्धियाँ	
by 12 months	Plays games with you, like pat-a-cake	आपके साथ गेम खेलता है, जैसे गाने की धुन पर आपस में ताली बजाना या घुघुआ मन्ना जैसे खेल	6 Month
	Language/Communication Milestones	भाषा/संचार संबंधी उपलब्धियाँ	
by 12 months	Waves “bye-bye”	हाथ हिलाकर "बाय-बाय" करता है	8 Month
by 12 months	Calls a parent “mama” or “dada” or another special name	माता-पिता को "मम्मा" या "बब्बा" या किसी अन्य विशेष नाम से पकारता है	6 Month
by 12 months	Understands “no” (pauses briefly or stops when you say it)	"ना" को समझता है (आपके कहने पर थोड़ा रुकता है या बिल्कुल रुक जाता है)	6 Month
	Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving)	संज्ञानात्मक उपलब्धियाँ (सीखना, सोचना, समस्या-समाधान)	
by 12 months	Puts something in a container, like a block in a cup	कन्टेनर में कुछ डालता है, जैसे एक कप में एक ब्लॉक	9 Month
by 12 months	Looks for things he sees you hide, like a toy under a blanket	उन चीजों की तलाश करता है जिन्हें वह आपको छिपाता हुआ देखता है, जैसे कि आप कम्बल के नीचे एक खिलौने को छिपाते हैं	10 Month
	Movement/Physical Development Milestones	गतिविधि / शारीरिक विकास की उपलब्धियाँ	
by 12 months	Pulls up to stand	खड़े होने के लिए खुद को ऊपर की ओर खींचता है	7 Month
by 12 months	Walks, holding on to furniture	फर्नीचर को पकड़े हुए चलता है	8 Month
by 12 months	Drinks from a cup without a lid, as you hold it	आपके हाथ से पकड़े हुए, बिना ढक्कन वाले प्याले से पीता है	9 Month
by 12 months	Picks things up between thumb and pointer finger, like small bits of food	अंगूठे और तर्जनी के बीच चीजों को उठाता है, जैसे भोजन के छोटे टुकड़े	8 Month
	Social/Emotional Milestones	सामाजिक/भावनात्मक उपलब्धियाँ	
by 15 months	Copies other children while playing, like taking toys out of a container when another child does	खेलते समय अन्य बच्चों की नकल करता है, जैसे किसी अन्य बच्चे द्वारा खिलौनों को कन्टेनर से बाहर निकालना	8 Month
by 15 months	Shows you an object she likes	आपको वह उसकी पसंद की वस्तु दिखाता है	9 Month
by 15 months	Claps when excited	उत्साहित होने पर ताली बजाता है	8 Month
by 15 months	Hugs stuffed doll or other toy	रुई से भरे खिलौने या अन्य खिलौने को गले लगाता है	9 Month
by 15 months	Shows you affection (hugs, cuddles, or kisses you)	आपको स्नेह दिखाता है (गले लगाना, चिपकना, या आपको चुमना)	9 Month
	Language/Communication Milestones	भाषा/संचार संबंधी उपलब्धियाँ	
by 15 months	Tries to say one or two words besides “mama” or “dada,” like “ba” for ball or “da” for dog	मम्मा" या "बब्बा" के अलावा एक या दो शब्द कहने की कोशिश करता है, जैसे गेंद के लिए "बो" या कत्ते के लिए "डो"	8 Month
by 15 months	Looks at a familiar object when you name it	जब आप किसी परिचित वस्तु का नाम लेते हैं तो वह देखता है	4 Month

by 15 months	Follows directions given with both a gesture and words. For example, he gives you a toy when you hold out your hand and say, "Give me the toy."	हावभाव और शब्दों, दोनों के साथ दिए गए निर्देशों का पालन करता है। उदाहरण के लिए, जब आप अपना हाथ आगे कर के कहते हैं, "मुझे खिलौना दो", तो वह आपको एक खिलौना देता है।	6 Month
by 15 months	Points to ask for something or to get help	कुछ माँगने या मदद पाने के लिए उंगली से इशारा करता है।	7 Month
	Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving)	संज्ञानात्मक उपलब्धियाँ (सीखना, सोचना, समस्या-समाधान)	
by 15 months	Tries to use things the right way, like a phone, cup, or book	चीजों को सही तरीके से इस्तेमाल करने की कोशिश करता है, जैसे फोन, कप या किताब/ कंकड़ों को कप में डाल सकता है।	9 Month
by 15 months	Stacks at least two small objects, like blocks	कम से कम दो छोटी वस्तुओं को एक के ऊपर एक रखता है, जैसे कि ब्लॉक	10 Month
	Movement/Physical Development Milestones	गतिविधि / शारीरिक विकास की उपलब्धियाँ	
by 15 months	Takes a few steps on his own	अपने दम पर कुछ कदम उठाता है	10 Month
by 15 months	Uses fingers to feed herself some food	खुद कुछ खाने के लिए उंगलियों का इस्तेमाल करता है	9 Month
	Social/Emotional Milestones	सामाजिक/भावनात्मक उपलब्धियाँ	
by 18 months	Moves away from you, but looks to make sure you are close by	आपसे दूर जाता है, लेकिन यह सुनिश्चित करता है कि आप करीब हैं	5 Month
by 18 months	Points to show you something interesting	आपको कुछ दिलचस्प दिखाने के लिए उंगली से इशारा करता है	8 Month
by 18 months	Puts hands out for you to wash them	हाथ धोने के लिए आगे करता है	9 Month
by 18 months	Looks at a few pages in a book with you	आपके साथ किसी किताब के कुछ पन्ने देखता है	9 Month
by 18 months	Helps you dress him by pushing arm through sleeve or lifting up foot	आस्तीन के बाहर हाथ निकालकर या पैर ऊपर उठाकर खुद तैयार होने में आपकी सहायता करता है	8 Month
	Language/Communication Milestones	भाषा/संचार संबंधी उपलब्धियाँ	
by 18 months	Tries to say three or more words besides "mama" or "dada"	"ममा" या "डैडा" के अलावा तीन या अधिक शब्द कहने का प्रयास करता है	10 Month
by 18 months	Follows one-step directions without any gestures, like giving you the toy when you say, "Give it to me."	बिना किसी इशारों के एक-चरणीय के निर्देशों का पालन करता है, जैसे कि जब आप कहते हैं, "मुझे दो।"	9 Month
	Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving)	संज्ञानात्मक उपलब्धियाँ (सीखना, सोचना, समस्या-समाधान)	
by 18 months	Copies you doing chores, like sweeping with a broom	आपके द्वारा किए जाने वाले कामों की नकल करता है, जैसे झाड़ू लगाना	10 Month
by 18 months	Plays with toys in a simple way, like pushing a toy car	खिलौनों के साथ सरल तरीके से खेलता है, जैसे किसी छोटी कार को धक्का देना	10 Month
	Movement/Physical Development Milestones	गतिविधि / शारीरिक विकास की उपलब्धियाँ	
by 18 months	Walks without holding on to anyone or anything	किसी व्यक्ति या चीज़ को पकड़े बिना चलता है	11 Month

by 18 months	Scribbles	आड़ी-तिरछी रेखाएँ बनाता है	11 Month
by 18 months	Drinks from a cup without a lid and may spill sometimes	बिना ढक्कन वाले प्याले से पीता है और कभी-कभी गिरा सकता है	10 Month
by 18 months	Feeds herself with her fingers	अपनी उंगलियों से खूद खाता है	11 Month
by 18 months	Tries to use a spoon	चम्मच का उपयोग करने की कोशिश करता है	10 Month
by 18 months	Climbs on and off a couch or chair without help	बिना मदद के सोफे या कुर्सी पर चढ़ता-उतरता है	11 Month
	Social/Emotional Milestones		
		सामाजिक/भावनात्मक उपलब्धियाँ	
by 2 years	Notices when others are hurt or upset, like pausing or looking sad when someone is crying	जब दूसरों को चोट लगती है या परेशान होते हैं तो ध्यान देता है, जैसे किसी के रोने पर रुकना या उदास दिखना	10 Month
by 2 years	Looks at your face to see how to react in a new situation	नई स्थिति में कैसे प्रतिक्रिया दी जाए यह देखने के लिए आपके चेहरे को देखता है	8 Month
	Language/Communication Milestones		
		भाषा/संचार संबंधी उपलब्धियाँ	
by 2 years	Points to things in a book when you ask, like "Where is the bear?"	जब आप पूछते हैं जैसे "भालू कहाँ है?", तो किताब में चीजों की ओर इशारा करता है	8 Month
by 2 years	Says at least two words together, like "More milk."	कम से कम दो शब्द एक साथ कहता है, जैसे "ज्यादा दूध।"	11 Month
by 2 years	Points to at least two body parts when you ask him to show you	जब आप उसे आपको अंग दिखाने के लिए कहते हैं तो शरीर के कम से कम दो अंगों की ओर इशारा करता है	11 Month
by 2 years	Uses more gestures than just waving and pointing, like blowing a kiss or nodding yes	सिर्फ हाथ हिलाने और इशारा करने से ज्यादा चेष्टाओं का उपयोग करता है, जैसे चूंबन देना या हाँ में सिर हिलाना	10 Month
	Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving)		
		संज्ञानात्मक उपलब्धियाँ (सीखना, सोचना, समस्या-समाधान)	
by 2 years	Holds something in one hand while using the other hand; for example, holding a container and taking the lid off	दूसरे हाथ का उपयोग करते समय एक हाथ में कुछ पकड़ता है; उदाहरण के लिए, कटेनर को पकड़कर ढक्कन खोलना	11 Month
by 2 years	Tries to use switches, knobs, or buttons on a toy	खिलौने की स्विच, नाँब या बटन का उपयोग करने की कोशिश करता है	11 Month
by 2 years	Plays with more than one toy at the same time, like putting toy food on a toy plate	एक ही समय में एक से अधिक खिलौनों के साथ खेलता है, जैसे टॉय प्लेट पर टॉय फूड रखना	10 Month
	Movement/Physical Development Milestones		
		गतिविधि / शारीरिक विकास की उपलब्धियाँ	
by 2 years	Kicks a ball	गेंद को लात मारता है	11 Month
by 2 years	Runs	दौड़ता है	12 Month
by 2 years	Walks (not climbs) up a few stairs with or without help	मदद के साथ या बिना कुछ सीढ़ियों पर चलकर आगे बढ़ता है (चढ़ता नहीं है)	12 Month
by 2 years	Eats with a spoon	चम्मच से खाता है	11 Month

Social/Emotional Milestones of Garbhotsav Child

Figure 5: Social/Emotional Milestones of the child from birth till the age of 2 years. The X-axis shows the months. The Y-axis gives the number for the milestone listed on the right side of the graph. The Green bar gives the month in which the milestone should be normally achieved as per scale by a normal child (Zubler et al., 2022; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025a; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025b; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025c). The Purple bar gives the month in which the milestone was achieved by the Garbhotsav child.

Language/Communication Milestones of Garbhotsav Child

Figure 6: Language/Communication Milestones of the child from birth till the age of 2 years. The X-axis shows the months. The Y-axis gives the number for the milestone listed on the right side of the graph. The Green bar gives the month in which the milestone should be normally achieved as per scale by a normal child (Zubler et al., 2022; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025a; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025b; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025c). The Purple bar gives the month in which the milestone was achieved by the Garbhotsav child.

Figure 7: Cognitive Milestones (learning, thinking, problem-solving) of the child from birth till the age of 2 years. The X-axis shows the months. The Y-axis gives the number for the milestone listed on the right side of the graph. The Green bar gives the month in which the milestone should be normally achieved as per scale by a normal child (Zubler et al., 2022; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025a; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025b; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025c). The Purple bar gives the month in which the milestone was achieved by the Garbhotsav child.

Movement/Physical Development Milestones of Garbhotsav Child

Figure 8: Movement/Physical Development Milestones of the child from birth till the age of 2 years. The X-axis shows the months. The Y-axis gives the number for the milestone listed on the right side of the graph. The Green bar gives the month in which the milestone should be normally achieved as per scale by a normal child (Zubler et al., 2022; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025a; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025b; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2025c). The Purple bar gives the month in which the milestone was achieved by the Garbhotsav child.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This is an observational case-study showing the impact of “Gharbhotsav Sanskar” training module under the movement “Aao Gadhe Sanskarwan Peedhi”, run by Shantikunj, Haridwar. It illustrates the impact of basic elements of the ancient Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) on the overall health (physical, mental, emotional, spiritual health, and familial/social relation) of a pregnant woman, as well as on the developmental milestones of the new-born child from birth up to 2 years.

The pregnant woman was asked questions, from a questionnaire (Annexure 5), which conveys changes in her overall health (physical, mental, emotional, spiritual health, and familial/social relation) before and after adopting the ideal daily routine. The answers of the pregnant woman (Table 2 and Figures 1 to 4) suggest that the ideal daily routine, diet, conduct, yogabhyas, etc., based on basic elements of ancient IKS definitely had a positive/constructive/healthy impact on the overall health of the pregnant woman.

Through the Questionnaire given in Annexure 6, questions were asked to the mother about the developmental milestones of the new-born child from birth till the age of 2 years. The answers of the mother (Table 3 and Figures 5 to 8) depict that more than 90% of the milestones had been achieved by the new-born child earlier than those expected for a normal child. Also, it is especially noteworthy that all the milestones from 12 months up to 2 years had been achieved by the new-born child in less than or equal to 12 months (Table 3 and Figures 5 to 8), indicating the birth of a brighter and virtuous offspring. Thus, the basic elements of ancient IKS definitely have a positive impact on the development of the new-born child.

The observed results may be attributed to the constructive influence of the integrative IKS based approach adopted in the present study; a brief overview of the same is presented as follows.

4.1 Garbhotsav Sanskar ceremony (womb ceremony)

Various components of the Garbhotsav Sanskar ceremony (womb ceremony) have multi-dimensional constructive inspirations and impacts with regards to the overall health of the pregnant woman and fetus.

In *Pavitrikarana*, the ceremony begins with the sprinkling of water while sitting in a meditative posture; this is done with the intention of purifying the mind, body, and emotions to nurture pure feelings in the parents and the unborn child. The ritualistic water sprinkling and intention-setting act as a psychological grounding technique, actively shifting the nervous system from a state of distraction to focused calmness (Sharma, 2015a; Nielsen et al., 2026). From the perspective of Ayurveda, physical cleanliness (*Shaucha*) and mental purity (*Sattvavajaya*) are the first steps to balancing the *Prana Vata*, the subtle energy that governs the mind and sensory perception (Sharma, 2008; Murthy, 2008).

In *Surya Dhyan-Pranayama* (Sun meditation and breathing), the pregnant woman takes deep breaths while meditating on the sun, envisioning the absorption of vital life force (Prana) to increase physical, mental, and spiritual strength for both herself and the fetus. This was also advised to be a part of her daily routine. Deep, slow yogic breathing (Pranayama) significantly increases vagal parasympathetic tone and reduces sympathetic activity, which enhances maternal cardiovascular efficiency and normalizes fetal heart rate (Vasundhara, et

al., 2023). From the perspective of Ayurveda, the Sun represents cosmic *Agni* (fire/metabolism). Absorbing this energy is supposed to build *Ojas* (vital immunity and radiance) in the pregnant woman, as well as the developing fetus (Sharma, 2008; Murthy, 2008).

In *Chandan Dharanam* (applying sandalwood / tilak on the forehead), a mark (tilak) is applied to the forehead to invoke peace in the brain and prevent undue excitement. From the perspective of Ayurveda, Sandalwood possesses *Sheeta Veerya* (cooling energy). Applying it pacifies the *Pitta* dosha, preventing heat-induced agitation and anger in the mind (Gupta, 2005; Misra & Vaisya, 2013; Murthy, 2016).

In *Sankalpa, Kalash Pujan and Guru Vandana* (pledge and divine invocation), participants tie a sacred thread (*Kalava*) and take a vow to follow moral disciplines. They then worship a water pot (Kalash) representing the universe and pay reverence to the spiritual guide (Guru) for guidance. From a psychological perspective, publicly taking a pledge creates 'implementation intentions', highly increasing the psychological adherence to the healthy lifestyle habits pledged by the parents (Gollwitzer, 1999). Invoking a higher power and expressing gratitude fosters a deep sense of social and spiritual support, buffering against prenatal anxiety and isolation.

In *Aushadhi Avaghrana* (herbal inhalation and consumption), the pregnant woman smells a ground mixture prepared from parts of three medicinal plants, i.e. Banyan (*Ficus benghalensis*), Giloy (*Tinospora cordifolia*), and Peepal (*Ficus religiosa*). These represent vastness/longevity, disease resistance/upward growth, and supreme compassion, respectively (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Sharma, 2015a; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b). Giloy (*Tinospora cordifolia*) is a scientifically proven immunomodulator and antioxidant that protects against oxidative stress (Gupta et al., 2024). From the perspective of Ayurveda, these herbs are potent *Rasayanas* (rejuvenators) that nourish the *Rasa Dhatu* of the pregnant woman, which directly transfers to the *Upadhatu* (fetal tissue) (Sharma, 2008; Gupta, 2005).

In *Garbha Pujan and Ashwastana* (womb worship and assurance), the womb is worshiped as the abode of a divine representative. The pregnant woman, husband, and family explicitly pledge to create a peaceful, quarrel-free, and spiritually uplifting environment, accommodating the mother's dietary and emotional needs (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Sharma, 2015a; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b). Actively focusing love and reverence on the womb significantly enhances Maternal-Fetal Attachment (MFA) (the emotional, cognitive, and behavioral bond a mother develops with her unborn child); MFA serves as a foundational predictor for early childhood development, wherein higher levels of MFA are associated with superior neonatal emotional regulation and more optimal early childhood cognitive outcomes (Alhusen, 2008; Alhusen et al., 2013; Gioia, 2023).

In *Charu Pradan* (offering sweet rice pudding), the pregnant woman consumes *Kheer* (rice cooked with milk and sugar) as a blessed offering, symbolizing steadfastness (rice), purity (milk), and sweetness (sugar) (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Sharma, 2015a; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b). As per Ayurveda, milk and rice are *Sattvic* (pious) and *Jeevaniya* (life-giving) foods (Shetty et al., 2024; Sharma, 2008); their symbolic intake signifies consumption of *Sattvic* food items by the pregnant woman so that it may lead to the enhancement of *Ojas* (immunity) for herself and the fetus, and purify the mind.

In *Agni Sthapan and Mantra Ahuti* (fire ritual and oblations with mantras), lamps are lit to symbolize the awakening of righteous wisdom and divine consciousness. Oblations are offered while chanting the Gayatri and Mahamrityunjaya mantras for the physical and spiritual health of the child (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Sharma, 2015a; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b). Rhythmic recitation of complex Sanskrit mantras induces a state of neuro-cardiovascular synchronization, slowing respiration to roughly 6 breaths per minute, which optimizes blood pressure and autonomic nervous system efficiency (Bernardi et al., 2001). The chanting of Gayatri Mantra causes beneficial effects with regards to various physical and mental conditions like attention, concentration, contentment and well-being (Brahmavarchas, 2012a; Brahmavarchas, 2012b; Malhotra et al., 2016; Pradhan & Derle, 2012; Sharma & Kumar, 2025; Sharma, 2010a; Sharma, 2010b). With regards to the positive impact of Sanskrit mantra chanting on the sections of the brain dealing with phonetic processing and focused attention, the paper by Hartzell et al. (2016) about the Sanskrit Effect offers encouraging cues. The fire represents the transformation of material resources into subtle, spiritual energy, instilling a sense of purpose and selflessness in the parents (Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998d; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Brahmavarchas, 2016c; Mishra & Mishra, 2024; Pandya, 2009; Pandya, 2019; Sharma, 2022; Sharma, n.d.; Shrivastava et al., 2020a; Mishra & Mishra, 2024b; Mishra et al., 2019a; Shrivastava et al., 2019a; Shrivastava et al., 2019b; Mishra et al., 2019b; Shrivastava et al., 2019c; Shrivastava et al., 2020b).

In *Shanti Abhisinchanam* (sprinkling water for all round peace), water infused with positive vibrations is sprinkled to establish all round peace (Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell, 2020a; Brahmavarchas, 2016a; Sharma, 2015a; Brahmavarchas, 1998a; Brahmavarchas, 1998b). This provides a definitive emotional closure to the ritual, leaving the pregnant woman with a lingering psychological "afterglow" of safety, serenity, and community support, which sustains her mental health in the days following the ceremony.

4.2 The promises made by the expecting mother and her family during the Garbhotsav Sanskar (womb ceremony) act as a comprehensive biopsychosocial and spiritual intervention. By integrating dietary disciplines, emotional regulation, auditory stimulation, and family support, these pledges directly influence the physiological and neurobiological environment of the womb. A scientific analysis of the physical, mental, emotional, neurodevelopmental, and spiritual impacts of these promises is as follows.

(i) **Physical Impact (Mother and Fetus)** - Mother's pledges regarding hydration, yoga, balanced vegetarian diet, and avoiding lethargy (Promises 1, 2, 3, 6); Family's pledge to provide healthy food and keep the baby away from intoxicants and smoking (Family Promises 3, 5). **Maternal Impact:** Drinking adequate water in the morning (Ushapan) and maintaining a balanced, pure diet is supposed to prevent common pregnancy complications like severe constipation (Trottier et al., 2012) and gestational hypertension (Kibret et al., 2019). Regular practice of yogic exercises and Pranayama (Promise 3) improves maternal lumbopelvic stability (Holden et al., 2019), reduces mechanical lower back pain (Wadhwa et al., 2020). **Fetal Impact:** A nutrient-dense, vegetarian diet rich in legumes and dairy provides the essential elements like folate necessary for optimal fetal growth (MRC Vitamin Study Research Group, 1991), especially the nervous system. It increases bodily kinesthetic intelligence of mother and baby. Furthermore, the strict family pledge to stay away from smoking and intoxicants (Family Promise 3) prevents various adverse pregnancy outcomes caused by smoking (Mund et al., 2013), and alcohol.

(ii) **Mental and Emotional Impact (Mother and Fetus)** - Mother's pledges to remain happy,

avoid anger/jealousy, and avoid terrifying videos/literature (Promises 9, 11, 13, 15); Family's pledge to create a serene, abuse-free, and supportive environment (Family Promises 2, 4, 6). Maternal Impact: The family's commitment to avoiding strife and fulfilling the mother's righteous desires acts as a critical buffer against prenatal depression and anxiety. High social support (Tadanki et al., 2025) and intentional emotional regulation (refraining from anger and negative thoughts) downregulate the maternal autonomic nervous system. Fetal Impact: The emotional state of the mother biologically translates to the fetus via the placenta (Pino et al., 2023). Chronic maternal distress, anger, or exposure to terrifying media triggers the release of maternal cortisol, which in turn has a negative impact on the fetus (Pino et al., 2023). The pledges to maintain a peaceful, loving environment actively protect the fetus.

(iii) Neurodevelopmental Impact (Fetus) - Mother's pledge to provide at least four hours of quality sound exposure (soothing music, discourses, stories, chanting) and to read inspiring literature (Promises 8, 14). Maternal Impact: Engaging with positive literature and music induces a state of relaxation (Provasi et al., 2021; Pino et al., 2023). Fetal Impact: The fetal auditory system is functional by the third trimester. Providing structured, repetitive, and high-quality sound exposure (like rhythmic reading, chanting, positive storytelling, and melodious music) bathe the fetus in a rich environment of varied rhythmic stimuli (Provasi et al., 2021). Research demonstrates that the fetus actively learns to recognize maternal voice intonations and rhythmic patterns in utero, which lays the foundational neural architecture for postnatal language acquisition and cognitive processing (Partanen et al., 2013).

(iv) Spiritual Impact (Mother and Fetus) - Mother's pledges to meditate, chant mantras, read religious texts, and view food as a divine offering (Promises 4, 5, 7); Family's pledge to view the baby as a representative of the Almighty (Family Promise 1). Maternal Impact: Spiritual practices such as chanting mantras and meditating provide existential grounding and robust coping mechanisms. They increase intrapersonal and existential intelligence in mother and fetus. Fetal Impact (Maternal-Fetal Attachment): Viewing the unborn baby not just as a biological entity, but as a "divine soul" or "representative of the Almighty," profoundly elevates Maternal-Fetal Attachment (MFA) (the emotional, cognitive, and behavioral bond a mother develops with her unborn child); MFA serves as a foundational predictor for early childhood development, wherein higher levels of MFA are associated with superior neonatal emotional regulation and more optimal early childhood cognitive outcomes (Alhusen, 2008; Alhusen et al., 2013; Gioia, 2023).

4.3 Ideal Daily Routine

An ideal daily routine based on the basic tenets of Indian Knowledge Systems had been prescribed to the pregnant woman and she diligently followed the same in the present study. The possible contribution of various components of the ideal daily routine in the observed outcomes may be understood as follows.

Waking up Before Sunrise and Ushapan: The pregnant woman was advised to wake up early, ideally before sunrise, and do *Ushapan*, *i.e.* drinking plain or lukewarm water on an empty stomach in the morning. In Ayurveda, the morning time of about 1.5 hours before sunrise is known as *Brahmamuhurta*, a time when the environment is saturated with *Sattva* (purity) and the body's *Vata* dosha is naturally dominant (Gupta, 2005). Waking at this time aligns the biological clock with nature, aiding in the smooth elimination of physical and mental waste (Gupta, 2005). Ayurveda explicitly dictates waking during this period for the preservation of health (Gupta, 2005). Current integrative research validates this concept, demonstrating that aligning with natural circadian rhythms stabilizes the autonomic nervous system and tightly

regulates the rhythmic secretion of maternal cortisol (Astiz & Oster, 2018; Hsu & Tain, 2020). *Ushapan* acts to flush the gastrointestinal tract and gently stimulate the *Agni* (digestive fire) (Gupta, 2005).

Womb Conversation and Positive Auditory Stimulation: The integrative IKS based approach strongly emphasizes positively impacting the auditory environment of the fetus for about four hours daily through womb conversation (talking to the baby affectionately), playing soft, melodious, soothing music, rhythmic chanting of mantras like the Gayatri Mantra, and creating a cheerful, positive ambiance. Ayurveda states that the fetus develops a mind and begins to express desires through the mother around the third to fourth month of gestation, a phase called *Dauhrida* or the "two hearts" state (Murthy, 2008). Fulfilling these emotional desires with positive stimuli, like the vibration of mantras and classical music, acts as subtle nourishment (*Sukshma Ahara*) and directly shapes the *Manasika Prakriti* (psychological constitution) of the baby (Murthy, 2008).

As per modern medical science, hearing requires the mechanosensitive hair cells located strictly within the Organ of Corti (Roccio et al., 2018; Jankovic-Raznatovic et al., 2014). This human inner ear is developed during the early fetal stage, specifically weeks 8 to 12 post-conception, which is the exact critical window when the prosensory domain becomes specified (Roccio et al., 2018; Jankovic-Raznatovic et al., 2014). Furthermore, the fetal auditory system becomes functional around the third trimester (specifically between 24 to 28 weeks of gestation) (Ullal-Gupta et al., 2013). This development during the third trimester initiates a complex process of auditory learning, allowing the fetus to familiarize itself with external sounds such as voices and music before birth (Ullal-Gupta et al., 2013). So, the auditory practices mentioned in this paper do have a profound, dual-layered impact on fetal neurodevelopment. Contemporary studies corroborate this ancient view, demonstrating that prenatal exposure to auditory stimuli, such as music and speech, facilitates the formation of stimulus-specific memory traces in the fetus (Movalled et al., 2023). This neurobiological priming affects the neonatal nervous system, enabling infants to recognize prenatal sounds and achieve superior scores on neonatal behavioral assessments (Movalled et al., 2023).

Through Womb Conversation, the expectant mother is encouraged to affectionately talk to the fetus and tell inspiring tales, as well as mentally or rhythmically chant hymns. The maternal voice is transmitted to the fetus not just through the air, but via bone and fluid conduction through the mother's body (Krueger, 2010). As mentioned above, by the third trimester, the fetus actively listens to the rhythm, melody, and intonation (the "prosody") of the mother's language (Ullal-Gupta et al., 2013). Rhythmic chanting (like reciting mantras or poetry) provides highly structured, repetitive auditory stimuli (Provasi et al., 2021). Maternal vocalizations, including speaking, singing, and chanting, bathe the fetus in a rich environment of varied rhythmic stimuli (Provasi et al., 2021). Research shows that fetuses can distinguish their mother's voice from a stranger's (Kisilevsky et al., 2003) and can even recognize specific rhythmic patterns they hear repeatedly in utero (Partanen et al., 2013). This repeated exposure triggers neural plasticity in the developing auditory cortex, literally laying the architectural groundwork for postnatal speech processing and language acquisition (Partanen et al., 2013; Kisilevsky et al., 2003).

The paper suggests combining music and chanting with devout meditation to drain out "negativity" and "evil instincts". The most significant impact of listening to soothing music and chanting mantras along with meditation is that it relaxes the expectant mother. Maternal stress alters the intrauterine environment by driving epigenetic changes in the placenta, specifically concerning genes involved in cortisol and serotonin responses, which can

negatively alter the trajectory of fetal neurodevelopment (Pino et al., 2023). When a pregnant woman engages in relaxing auditory practices, her parasympathetic nervous system engages (Pino et al., 2023). This lowers her circulating cortisol and adrenaline (Pino et al., 2023). Thus, utilizing prenatal musical stimulation acts as a powerful environmental intervention that effectively regulates these maternal stress responses (Pino et al., 2023). By promoting maternal emotional homeostasis, music therapy influences this "placental programming" to mitigate the transfer of stress hormones, actively protecting the developing fetal brain from stress-induced neurobehavioral changes and supporting healthy structural development (Pino et al., 2023). It also has positive effect on verbal linguistic intelligence.

Yogic Practices: The integrative approach promotes Yogic practices and advises pregnant woman to avoid negative thoughts and violent media.

From an Ayurvedic perspective, the mind and body are considered inseparable in Ayurveda (Sharma, 2008). The *Charaka Samhita* specifically notes that a mother afflicted by grief, anger, or fear (*Shoka, Krodha, Bhaya*) directly transmits this vitiated energy to the fetus, which can negatively impact the child's future psychological resilience (Sharma, 2008). Excessive stress or fear vitiates the *Vata* dosha, including the *Prana Vata* (governing the mind) and *Apana Vata* (governing the pelvic region) (Gupta, 2005; Sharma, 2008; Sumantran & Nair, 2019). *Pranayama* naturally balances these air currents (*Vata Anulomana*), ensuring a calm mind (Rawal et al., 2019; Sharma, 2008). Furthermore, the pregnant woman is prescribed *Sadvritta* (the code of noble conduct) to maintain emotional equilibrium (Sharma, 2008).

Modern researches have ascertained that Yogic practices are safe and effective during pregnancy (Polis et al., 2015a; Polis et al., 2015b; Field et al., 2013; Wadhwa et al., 2020; Holden et al., 2019). Field et al. (2013) showed that in prenatally depressed women, Yogic intervention lowered long-term depression, anxiety, anger, and cortisol levels into the postpartum period, as well as provided immediate relief from negative moods and physical pain. Meditation (*Dhyan*) decreases cortisol and adrenaline levels, and increases endorphin hormone (happy hormone), which reduces tension and stress (Lutz et al., 2008-a; Lutz et al., 2008-b; Philip et al., 2025; Venditt et al., 2020; Pascoe et al., 2021). Meditation alters neural circuitry, leading to improved emotional balance, reduced physiological reactivity to stress, and an overall reduction in tension, promoting well-being (Lutz et al., 2008-a; Lutz et al., 2008-b).

Sattvic Diet: The integrative approach advises eating pure, balanced, vegetarian (*Sattvic*) food. A pregnant woman's diet is meant to build *Ojas* - the ultimate essence of tissue vitality and immunity for both herself and the fetus (Sharma, 2008). A *Sattvic* diet ensures the food is easy to digest and creates mental clarity rather than lethargy or agitation (Sharma, 2008). Recent scientific studies reveal that traditional, nutrient-dense, plant-based dietary patterns support positive mental health (Lachance & Ramsey, 2015; Logan & Jacka, 2014; Berding et al., 2021).

Milk, with a pinch of turmeric, has been recommended in the *Sattvic* diet. Milk is universally revered in Ayurveda as a *Jeevaniya* (life-promoting) substance (Shetty et al., 2024; Sharma, 2008). The addition of turmeric provides anti-inflammatory benefits, while honey acts as a *Yogavahi* (a catalytic carrier, i.e. having the ability to carry, amplify, and deliver the medicinal properties of the herbs or minerals it is mixed with, all without losing or altering its own inherent therapeutic qualities) (Sharma, 2008). This aligns with the *Charaka Samhita*, which outlines a specific month-by-month dietary regimen (*Masanumasika Paricharya*) relying on

milk and sweet-tasting herbs to nourish the fetus (Sharma, 2008). Charaka Samhita (Shareer Sthan, Chapter 8) (Sharma, 2008) advises a diet rich in the Madhura (sweet) group of foods, as this taste is anabolic and promotes tissue growth while pacifying Vata and Pitta doshas. The Sattvic diet recommended in this paper intuitively includes this through daily fruits, natural sweets, milk-based sweet kheer.

The Sattvic diet frequently utilizes green moong. In Ayurveda, this specific legume is considered Laghu (light to digest) and Balya (strength-promoting) (Sharma, 2008), making it ideal for maternal digestion, which can often be sluggish.

Thus, the dietary guidelines in the document effectively capture the psychological and Sattvic (pure, non-stimulating) spirit of Ayurvedic pregnancy care. Furthermore, nutritionally, recommended Sattvic diet bridges ancient wisdom with modern dietetics, by incorporating modern vegetarian diet rich in complex carbohydrates, fiber, and legume-based proteins, which are found to be beneficial during pregnancy (Trottier et al., 2012; Kibret et al., 2019). With regards to intake of nuts like walnuts and almonds, consuming more nuts during early pregnancy is linked to improved cognitive and neurodevelopmental outcomes in children at ages 1.5, 5, and 8 years (Gignac et al., 2019). Moong dal, gram, etc. are excellent natural source of folate; optimal folate levels during early pregnancy are known to significantly reduce the risk of Neural Tube Defects like spina bifida (MRC Vitamin Study Research Group, 1991), anencephaly, meningocele, myelomeningocele, etc.

4.4 Impact of Prenatal Practices on Child Development

Epigenetics and fetal programming reveal that environmental factors such as maternal nutrition, stress, and lifestyle dynamically alter gene expression without changing the underlying DNA sequence (Saraswat & Sharma, 2026; Wiley et al., 2023; Zuccarello et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2019; Kappil et al., 2016; Lacagnina, 2019). The initial 1,000 days of life, spanning conception through early childhood, serve as a critical window where these external variables permanently shape an individual's lifelong physical and psychological health trajectories (Saraswat & Sharma, 2026). This paradigm highlights that parental health and early social experiences can even exert transgenerational effects (Saraswat & Sharma, 2026). By integrating these epigenetic insights into clinical frameworks, one can proactively design preventive healthcare strategies, empowering parents and practitioners to build a significantly healthier, more resilient foundation for future generations (Saraswat & Sharma, 2026).

The practices observed during pregnancy, ranging from dietary disciplines and yoga to emotional regulation and spiritual ceremonies like Garbhotsav Sanskar, function as a comprehensive system of fetal programming (Saraswat & Sharma, 2026). The upbringing of a child essentially begins in the womb, where a major portion of the development is completed before birth (Saraswat & Sharma, 2026). The subconscious mind of the fetus actively records and assimilates the mother's feelings, perceptions, and experiences (Saraswat & Sharma, 2026). A brief overview of how these prenatal practices impact the child physically, mentally, emotionally, and spiritually after birth is as follows.

(i) **Physical Impact (Immunity and Metabolic Health):** This paper states that babies born to mothers who maintain a positive attitude, consume a balanced and pure diet, and practice yoga are generally found to be healthy, relaxed, and physically capable of coping well in life. Conversely, maternal malnutrition or high stress can result in the child developing roots of adult-onset diseases like high blood pressure, diabetes, and heart disease (Barker, 1990). The Developmental Origins of Health and Disease (DOHaD) paradigm, often linked to the Barker

Hypothesis, demonstrates that fetal adaptations to the intrauterine environment permanently program the child's metabolic and cardiovascular systems (Heindel & Vandenberg, 2015; Vickers, 2014). A nutrient-dense diet (rich in methyl donors like folate) can prevent structural maladaptations in fetal organs, drastically lowering the child's lifetime risk of metabolic and cardiovascular disorders (Vickers, 2014). Ayurveda states that the mother's Rasa Dhatu (nutrient plasma) directly nourishes the fetus (Upadhatu) (Sharma, 2008). A Sattvic (pure, fresh) diet and a disciplined routine build Ojas (the vital essence of immunity) in the mother, which is transferred to the child (Sharma, 2008). This transfer ensures the child is born with *Bala* (robust physical strength and innate immunity) (Sharma, 2008).

(ii) Neurodevelopmental Impact (Cognition and Brain Architecture): This paper states that consistent positive auditory stimulation (like soft music or womb conversation) enhances the productivity of fetal brain cells, leading to a child who is attentive, intelligent, and excels in academics, communication, and decision-making. The fetal auditory cortex is highly malleable. Structured, repetitive, and high-quality sound exposure (like rhythmic reading, chanting, positive storytelling, and melodious music) engulfs the fetus in a rich environment of varied rhythmic stimuli and can trigger synaptic response (Provasi et al., 2021). Research demonstrates that the fetus actively learns to recognize maternal voice intonations and rhythmic patterns in utero, which lays the foundational neural architecture for postnatal language acquisition and cognitive processing (Partanen et al., 2013). As per Ayurveda, the development of the Indriyas (sensory and motor organs) is heavily influenced by the Prana Vata (the subtle energy governing the nervous system). Regular Pranayama (breathing exercises) and a serene environment keep the mother's Vata balanced (Gupta, 2005), ensuring optimal oxygenation and proper fetal growth.

(iii) Emotional Impact (Stress Resilience and Attachment): This paper states that if a mother experiences continuous negative thinking, anger, tension, or sadness, the baby is highly likely to be born irritable, aggressive, frustrated, and mentally and emotionally disordered. A loving, conflict-free environment ensures the child develops good self-esteem and healthy relationship skills. Chronic maternal stress causes a sustained release of cortisol, which crosses the placenta (Pino et al., 2023). Prenatal yoga (Field et al., 2013) and a supportive family environment (Tadanki et al., 2025) actively lower maternal cortisol, protecting the child's emotional baseline. As per Ayurveda, during the Dauhrida (bi-cardiac) phase, the fetus expresses its emotional needs through the mother (Murthy, 2008). Fulfilling these desires and keeping the mother emotionally nourished establishes a stable Manasika Prakriti (psychological constitution) in the child (Murthy, 2008). Ignoring her emotional needs is explicitly stated in Ayurvedic texts as a cause of congenital emotional and psychological defects in the offspring (Murthy, 2008).

(iv) Spiritual and Behavioral Impact (Values and Consciousness): This paper states that creating a religious atmosphere, avoiding violent media, and reading inspiring texts of great personalities are practices aimed at ensuring a divine soul takes birth in a pious environment. The baby's subconscious mind records these higher human values. High Maternal-Fetal Attachment (MFA) predicts highly secure infant-mother attachment post-birth (Alhusen, 2008). Secure attachment is the primary psychological foundation for the development of empathy, prosocial behavior, and a deep sense of safety and connectedness to the broader world (Xu et al., 2022). Ayurveda states that the mind consists of three Gunas (qualities): Sattva (purity), Rajas (action), and Tamas (inertia). The ultimate goal of Garbha Sanskar and the following guidance (fetal programming) is to maximize the Sattva Guna. Chanting mantras, offering food as a divine blessing (Prasad), and maintaining noble conduct

(Sadvritta) imprint deeply upon the child's subtle body, orienting his inherent nature toward wisdom, compassion, and spiritual inclination from birth (Sharma, 2008).

Thus, this individual case study illustrates that if carefully formulated universal deliverables based on the basic elements of ancient Indian Knowledge Systems are communicated in the right spirit to the pregnant woman, her husband and family members, as well as the neighbors, then they can be motivated, encouraged, influenced and trained to bring out positivity in their behavior and change in their attitude, which in turn can lead to a positive impact on the overall health of the pregnant woman, as well as on the development of the new-born child. With close, continuous guidance and monitoring, these changes can also be made permanent and mandatory in individual lifestyle, society, as well as globally.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

A consent form (Annexure-2) was filled by the pregnant woman, wherein she agreed to participate in this study, and also agreed that her data can be used for research purposes, as well as for related publications and presentations. A Participant Information Sheet (Annexure-3) was also given to the pregnant woman and signed by her, which explains the details of this project.

Conflict of Interest

None.

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References

- Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell. (2020a). *Method of performing Garbh Sanskar* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=79JYFdItUM8>
- Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell. (2020b). सुसंस्कृत पीढ़ी का निर्माण कैसे करें ? *How to build cultured generation* [Dr. Gayatri Sharma] [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t_ut5To7F4Q
- Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell. (2022a). गर्भावस्था में आदर्श दिनचर्या - *Ideal daily routine during pregnancy* [Smt. Jyotsna Modi] [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L9fhxcAvi74>
- Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell. (2022b). *Yogasan, Pranayam and Dhyana- Dr Rashmi Sharma* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KPsKVXFBWMM>
- Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell. (2022c). गर्भावस्था में आहार- *Diet during pregnancy* [Dr. Anjali] [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-9h_ozGyYOG
- Aao Garhe Sanskarvan Pidhi Cell. (2025). गर्भ संवाद - *Womb conversation* [Smt. Sheela Dwivedi] [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dBme46YbS1A>
- Alhusen, J. L. (2008). A literature update on maternal-fetal attachment. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 37(3), 315–328. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.2008.00241.x>
- Alhusen, J. L., Hayat, M. J., & Gross, D. (2013). A longitudinal study of maternal attachment and infant developmental outcomes. *Archives of Women's Mental Health*, 16, 521–529. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00737-013-0357-8>
- Arora, L., Coe, E., Dewhurst, M., & Enomoto, K. (2022). *Heat waves, the war in Ukraine, and stigma: Gen Z's perspectives on mental health*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/mhi/our-insights/heat-waves-the-war-in-ukraine-and-stigma-gen-zs-perspectives-on-mental-health>
- Astiz, M., & Oster, H. (2018). Perinatal programming of circadian clock-stress crosstalk. *Neural Plasticity*, 2018, Article 5689165. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/5689165>
- Balchandani, A., et al. (2023). *What is Gen Z?*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/mckinsey-explainers/what-is-gen-z>
- Barker, D. J. (1990). The fetal and infant origins of adult disease. *BMJ*, 301(6761), 1111. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.301.6761.1111>

- Bayne, T., Frohlich, J., Cusack, R., Moser, J., & Naci, L. (2023). Consciousness in the cradle: On the emergence of infant experience. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 27(12), 1135–1149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2023.08.018>
- Berding, K., Vlekova, K., Marx, W., Schellekens, H., Stanton, C., Clarke, G., Jacka, F., Dinan, T. G., & Cryan, J. F. (2021). Diet and the microbiota-gut-brain axis: Sowing the seeds of good mental health. *Advances in Nutrition*, 12(4), 1239–1285. <https://doi.org/10.1093/advances/nmaa181>
- Bernardi, L., Sleight, P., Bandinelli, G., Cencetti, S., Fattorini, L., Wdowczyk-Szulc, J., & Lagi, A. (2001). Effect of rosary prayer and yoga mantras on autonomic cardiovascular rhythms: Comparative study. *BMJ*, 323(7327), 1446–1449. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.323.7327.1446>
- Brahmavarchas. (Ed.). (1998a). *Shodash sanskar vivechan* [Explanation of sixteen sacramental rites] (2nd ed., Vol. 33). Akhand Jyoti Sansthan. https://vicharkrantibooks.org/productdetail?book_name=HINB0151_33_SHODASH_SANSKAR_VIVECHAN_2nd1998&product_id=151
- Brahmavarchas. (Ed.). (1998b). *Hamari bhavi pidhi aur usaka navanirman* [Our future generation and its reconstruction] (2nd ed., Vol. 63). Akhand Jyoti Sansthan. https://vicharkrantibooks.org/productdetail?book_name=HINB0054_63_HAMARI_BHAVI_PIDHI_AUR_USAKA_NAVANIRMAN_2nd1998&product_id=54
- Brahmavarchas. (2016a). *Aao gadhen sanskarvan pidhi - 2 (Garbhotsav manaen)* [Let us create a cultured generation - 2 (Celebrate Garbhotsav)]. Shri Ved Mata Gayatri Trust. https://www.awgp.org/en/literature/book/aaogadhen_sanskarvan_pidhi_big/v1.2
- Brahmavarchas. (Ed.). (1998c). *Mahapurushon ke avismaraniya jeevan prasang-2* [Unforgettable life events of great personalities-2] (2nd ed., Vol. 51). Akhand Jyoti Sansthan. https://www.awgp.org/en/literature/book/Mahapurushon_Ke_Avismarniy_Prasang/v6
- Brahmavarchas. (2019). *Let us build a cultured generation*. Vedmata Gayatri Trust.
- Brahmavarchas. (2016b). *Aao gadhen swastha, pratibhashali, prakhar, tejasvi, buddhiman, sabhya, sanskarvan pidhi* [Let us build a healthy, talented, energetic, enlightened, intellectually sound, well-behaved, well-cultured generation]. Vedmata Gayatri Trust.
- Brahmavarchas. (1998d). *Yagya ka gyan-vigyan* [Pandit Shriram Sharma Acharya samagra vangamaya, Vol. 25]. Akhand Jyoti Sansthan. https://www.awgp.org/en/literature/book/yagya_ka_gyan_vigyan/v1
- Brahmavarchas. (2012a). *Shabda brahma - nad brahma* [Hindi] (2nd ed., Pandit Shriram Sharma Acharya samagra vangamaya, Vol. 19). Akhand Jyoti Sansthan. https://vicharkrantibooks.org/productdetail?book_name=HINB0146_19_SHABD_BRAHMA_NAD_BRAHM_2nd1998&product_id=146
- Brahmavarchas. (2012b). *Yagya - ek samagra upachar prakriya* [Hindi] (Rev. ed., Pandit Shriram Sharma Acharya samagra vangamaya, Vol. 26). Akhand Jyoti Sansthan. https://vicharkrantibooks.org/productdetail?book_name=HINB0180_26_YAGY_EK_SAMAGR_UPACHAR_PRAKRIYA_2nd1998&product_id=180
- Brahmavarchas. (2016c). *Yagya chikitsa*. Shri Vedmata Gayatri Trust (TMD), Shantikunj. https://vicharkrantibooks.org/Book_page/ViewPDF/3243
- Brassey, J., Herbig, B., Jeffery, B., & Ungerman, D. (2023). *Reframing employee health: Moving beyond burnout to holistic health*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/mhi/our-insights/reframing-employee-health-moving-beyond-burnout-to-holistic-health>

- Brower, T. (2025, December 7). *New data reveals what Gen Alpha wants most and how we should respond*. Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/tracybrower/2025/12/07/new-data-reveals-what-gen-alpha-wants-most-and-how-we-should-respond/>
- Callaghan, S., Doner, H., Medalsay, J., Pione, A., & Teichner, W. (2024). *The trends defining the \$1.8 trillion global wellness market in 2024*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/consumer-packaged-goods/our-insights/the-trends-defining-the-1-point-8-trillion-dollar-global-wellness-market-in-2024>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2025a). *CDC's developmental milestones*. U.S. Department of Health & Human Services. <https://www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/actearly/milestones/index.html>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2025b). *Milestone checklists with tips in all available languages (English)*. U.S. Department of Health & Human Services. <https://www.cdc.gov/act-early/resources/milestone-checklists.html>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2025c). *Milestone checklists with tips in all available languages (Hindi)*. U.S. Department of Health & Human Services. <https://www.cdc.gov/act-early/resources/milestone-checklists.html>
- Chen, J., Liu, Y., Dai, J., & Wang, C. (2023). Development and status of moral education research: Visual analysis based on knowledge graph. *Frontiers in Psychology, 13*, Article 1079955. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1079955>
- Coe, E., Cordina, J., Enomoto, K., & Jacobson, R. (2022). *Addressing the unprecedented behavioral-health challenges facing Generation Z*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/healthcare/our-insights/addressing-the-unprecedented-behavioral-health-challenges-facing-generation-z>
- Davis, E. P., & Sandman, C. A. (2010). The timing of prenatal exposure to maternal cortisol and psychosocial stress is associated with human infant cognitive development. *Child Development, 81*(1), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2009.01385.x>
- Dixit, S. A., Hiremath, K. V., Sharma, P., Kulkarni, V. G., & Shedbale, S. D. (2025). A review on pumsavana samskara: Revisiting the intersection of ritual, medicine, and foetal development in ayurveda. *International Journal of Research in Ayurveda and Pharmacy, 16*(5), 148–151. <https://doi.org/10.7897/2277-4343.165188>
- Doherty, J., Tueme, N., Koshiol, K., Evans, H., Bruce, T., & Patterson, A. (2024). *Thirteen: A first look at Gen Alpha*. Springtide Research Institute. <https://springtideresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/thirteen-a-first-look-at-gen-alpha-springtide-research-institute.pdf>
- Domingo, V., & Fernández Espinosa, V. (2025). Developing virtue-based leadership education: The Leaders of Character Program at Francisco de Vitoria University (Spain). *Journal of Moral Education, 1*–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057240.2025.2507910>
- Dunkel Schetter, C. (2011). Psychological science on pregnancy: Stress processes, biopsychosocial models, and emerging research issues. *Annual Review of Psychology, 62*, 531–558. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.031809.130727>
- Emde, R. N. (2016). From a baby smiling: Reflections on virtues in development. In J. Annas, D. Narvaez, & N. E. Snow (Eds.), *Developing the virtues: Integrating perspectives*. Oxford Academic. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780190271466.003.0004>
- Field, T., Diego, M., Delgado, J., & Medina, L. (2013). Yoga and social support reduce prenatal depression, anxiety and cortisol. *Journal of Bodywork and Movement Therapies, 17*(4), 397–403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbmt.2013.03.010>

- Francis, T., & Hoefel, F. (2018). *'True Gen': Generation Z and its implications for companies*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/consumer-packaged-goods/our-insights/true-generation-z-and-its-implications-for-companies>
- Gignac, F., Romaguera, D., Fernández-Barrés, S., Phillipat, C., Garcia Esteban, R., López-Vicente, M., Vioque, J., Fernández-Somoano, A., Tardón, A., Iñiguez, C., Lopez-Espinosa, M.-J., García de la Hera, M., Amiano, P., Ibarluzea, J., Guxens, M., Sunyer, J., & Julvez, J. (2019). Maternal nut intake in pregnancy and child neuropsychological development up to 8 years old: A population-based cohort study in Spain. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, 34, 661–673. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-019-00521-6>
- Gioia, M. C., Cerasa, A., Muggeo, V. M. R., Tonin, P., Cajiao, J., Aloï, A., Martino, I., Tenuta, F., Costabile, A., & Craig, F. (2023). The relationship between maternal-fetus attachment and perceived parental bonds in pregnant women: Considering a possible mediating role of psychological distress. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, Article 1095030. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1095030>
- Goldberg, H. (2022). Growing brains, nurturing minds: Neuroscience as an educational tool to support students' development as life-long learners. *Brain Sciences*, 12(12), Article 1622. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12121622>
- Gollwitzer, P. M. (1999). Implementation intentions: Strong effects of simple plans. *American Psychologist*, 54(7), 493–503. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.54.7.493>
- Gupta, A., Gupta, P., & Bajpai, G. (2024). *Tinospora cordifolia* (Giloy): An insight on the multifarious pharmacological paradigms of a most promising medicinal ayurvedic herb. *Heliyon*, 10(4), Article e26125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e26125>
- Gupta, K. A. (2005). *Ashtanga hrdayam of Vagbhata - Vidyotini Hindi commentary*. Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan.
- Hartzell, J. F., Davis, B., Melcher, D., Miceli, G., Jovicich, J., Nath, T., Chatterjee Singh, N., & Hasson, U. (2016). Brains of verbal memory specialists show anatomical differences in language, memory and visual systems. *NeuroImage*, 131, 181–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2015.07.027>
- Heindel, J. J., & Vandenberg, L. N. (2015). Developmental origins of health and disease: A paradigm for understanding disease cause and prevention. *Current Opinion in Pediatrics*, 27(2), 248–253. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MOP.0000000000000191>
- Holden, S. C., Manor, B., Zhou, J., Zera, C., Davis, R. B., & Yeh, G. Y. (2019). Prenatal yoga for back pain, balance, and maternal wellness: A randomized, controlled pilot study. *Global Advances in Health and Medicine*, 8, 2164956119870984. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2164956119870984>
- Hsu, C.-N., & Tain, Y.-L. (2020). Light and circadian signaling pathway in pregnancy: Programming of adult health and disease. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(6), Article 2232. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21062232>
- Jankovic-Raznatovic, S., Dragojevic-Dikic, S., Rakic, S., Nikolic, B., Plesinac, S., Tasic, L., Perisic, Z., Sovilj, M., Adamovic, T., & Koruga, D. (2014). Fetus sound stimulation: Cilia memristor effect of signal transduction. *BioMed Research International*, 2014, Article 273932. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/273932>
- Kappil, M., Wright, R. O., & Sanders, A. P. (2016). Developmental origins of common disease: Epigenetic contributions to obesity. *Annual Review of Genomics and Human Genetics*, 17, 177–192. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-genom-090314-050057>

- Kibret, K. T., Chojenta, C., Gresham, E., Tegegne, T. K., & Loxton, D. (2019). Maternal dietary patterns and risk of adverse pregnancy (hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and gestational diabetes mellitus) and birth (preterm birth and low birth weight) outcomes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Public Health Nutrition*, 22(3), 506–520. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1368980018002616>
- Kisilevsky, B. S., Hains, S. M., Lee, K., Xie, X., Huang, H., Ye, H. H., Zhang, K., & Wang, Z. (2003). Effects of experience on fetal voice recognition. *Psychological Science*, 14(3), 220–224. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9280.02435>
- Krueger, C. (2010). Exposure to maternal voice in preterm infants: A review. *Advances in Neonatal Care*, 10(1), 13–20. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ANC.0b013e3181cc3c69>
- Kulkarni, R., & Kulkarni, A. (n.d.). *Ayurvediya garbhsanskar* [Ayurvedic garbhsanskar] (3rd ed.). Diamond Pocket Books.
- Lacagnina, S. (2019). The developmental origins of health and disease (DOHaD). *American Journal of Lifestyle Medicine*, 14(1), 47–50. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1559827619879694>
- Lachance, L., & Ramsey, D. (2015). Food, mood, and brain health: Implications for the modern clinician. *Missouri Medicine*, 112(2), 111–115. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6170050/>
- Lapsley, D. (2025). The moral purpose of higher education: Articulacy, strong evaluation and the moral self. *Journal of Moral Education*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057240.2025.2588837>
- Lin, B., Kaliush, P. R., Conradt, E., Terrell, S., Neff, D., Allen, A. K., Smid, M. C., Monk, C., & Crowell, S. E. (2019). Intergenerational transmission of emotion dysregulation: Part I. Psychopathology, self-injury, and parasympathetic responsivity among pregnant women. *Development and Psychopathology*, 31(3), 817–831. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954579419000336>
- Logan, A. C., & Jacka, F. N. (2014). Nutritional psychiatry research: An emerging discipline and its intersection with global urbanization, environmental challenges and the evolutionary mismatch. *Journal of Physiological Anthropology*, 33(1), Article 22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1880-6805-33-22>
- Lufkin, B. (2021, July 1). *The damaging effects of 'boreout' at work*. BBC Worklife. <https://www.bbc.com/worklife/article/20210701-the-damaging-effects-of-boreout-at-work>
- Lutz, A., Brefczynski-Lewis, J., Johnstone, T., & Davidson, R. J. (2008b). Regulation of the neural circuitry of emotion by compassion meditation: Effects of meditative expertise. *PLoS One*, 3(3), Article e1897. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0001897>
- Lutz, A., Slagter, H. A., Dunne, J. D., & Davidson, R. J. (2008a). Attention regulation and monitoring in meditation. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 12(4), 163–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2008.01.005>
- Malhotra, V., Goel, N., Dhar, U., Garg, R., & Tripathi, Y. (2016). Comparison of mind control techniques: An assessment of reaction times. *Bangladesh Journal of Medical Science*, 15(4), 596–600. <https://www.banglajol.info/index.php/BJMS/article/view/30718>
- Martone, M. A. (1998). Developing virtuous children: A theological perspective. *Journal of Social Distress and the Homeless*, 7, 107–119. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1022984213361>
- Mata-McMahon, J., Haslip, M. J., & Schein, D. L. (2020). Connections, virtues, and meaning-making: How early childhood educators describe children's spirituality. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 48, 657–669. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-020-01026-8>

- Mishra, A., Batham, L., Verma, S., Mishra, S., & Shrivastava, V. (2019a). Management of the symptoms associated with osteoarthritis of the knee through an integrated approach including yagya therapy. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Yagya Research*, 2(2), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.36018/ijyr.v2i2.25>
- Mishra, A., Batham, L., Verma, S., Mishra, S., & Shrivastava, V. (2019b). Management of epileptic seizures through an integrated approach including yagya therapy. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Yagya Research*, 2(1), 52–64. <http://ijyr.dsvv.ac.in/index.php/ijyr/article/view/24>
- Mishra, S., & Mishra, A. (2024a). Yagya conveys enlightening philosophical teachings and is also a high level science: A discourse of Revered Pandit Shriram Sharma Acharya. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Yagya Research*, 7(2), 22–28. <http://ijyr.dsvv.ac.in/index.php/ijyr/article/view/129>
- Mishra, S., & Mishra, A. (2024b). Purification of the subtle realm through yagya: Philosophical principles and implications for attaining universal peace and well-being. *Dev Sanskriti Interdisciplinary International Journal*, 23, 14–23. <https://doi.org/10.36018/dsij.23.337>
- Misra, B., & Vaisya, R. (2013). *Bhavaprakasa of Sribhava Misra (including Bhavaprakasa Nighantu portion)* (Vidyotini Hindi commentary, Pt. 1). Chaukhambha Sanskrit Bhawan.
- Mori, F.-K., & Shimosawa, T. (2025). The fetal environment and the development of hypertension: The epigenetic modification by glucocorticoids. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 26(1), Article 420. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms26010420>
- Movalled, K., Sani, A., Nikniaz, L., & Ghojzadeh, M. (2023). The impact of sound stimulations during pregnancy on fetal learning: A systematic review. *BMC Pediatrics*, 23(1), Article 183. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-023-03990-7>
- MRC Vitamin Study Research Group. (1991). Prevention of neural tube defects: Results of the Medical Research Council Vitamin Study. *The Lancet*, 338(8760), 131–137. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-6736\(91\)90133-A](https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-6736(91)90133-A)
- Mulligan, C., D’Errico, N., Stees, J., & Hughes, D. (2012). Methylation changes at NR3C1 in newborns associate with maternal prenatal stress exposure and newborn birth weight. *Epigenetics*, 7(8), 853–857. <https://doi.org/10.4161/epi.21180>
- Mund, M., Louwen, F., Klingelhofer, D., & Gerber, A. (2013). Smoking and pregnancy—A review on the first major environmental risk factor of the unborn. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 10(12), 6485–6499. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph10126485>
- Murthy, K. R. S. (2008). *Susruta samhita* (Vols. 1-3). Chaukhambha Orientalia.
- Murthy, K. R. S. (2016). *Bhavaprakasa of Bhavamisra (including Nighantu portion)* (Vol. 1). Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy.
- Mustoe, A. C., Birnie, A. K., Korgan, A. C., Santo, J. B., & French, J. A. (2012). Natural variation in gestational cortisol is associated with patterns of growth in marmoset monkeys (*Callithrix geoffroyi*). *General and Comparative Endocrinology*, 175(3), 519–526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygcen.2011.12.020>
- Narvaez, D., Gleason, T., Tarsha, M., Woodbury, R., Cheng, Y., & Wang, L. (2021). Sociomoral temperament: A mediator between wellbeing and social outcomes in young children. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 742199. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.742199>
- Nielsen, T. H., Karlsen, N. W., Hoang, L. T. M., Dahlgaard, J., & Østergaard, E. B. (2026). Winter bathing: An ice-cold strategy for improving quality of life for people with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. *Healthcare*, 14(6), Article 752. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare14060752>

- Oldham, P., & McLoughlin, S. (2025). Character education empirical research: A thematic review and comparative content analysis. *Journal of Moral Education*, 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057240.2025.2480185>
- Pandya, P. (2009). *Applied science of yagya for health and environment*. Vedmata Gayatri Trust, Shantikunj. https://www.awgp.org/en/literature/book/Applied_Science_of_Yagya_for_Health_and_Environment/v1
- Pandya, P. (Speaker). (2019, September). *Shrimadbhagavad gita mein yagya vigyan ke vidhan* [Audio discourse in Hindi]. <https://sites.google.com/view/adhyatmik-kayakalp/navaratri-dr-pranav-pandya/2019-09-navaratri-dr-pranav-pandya>
- Parker, K., & Igielnik, R. (2020). *On the cusp of adulthood and facing an uncertain future: What we know about Gen Z so far*. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2020/05/14/on-the-cusp-of-adulthood-and-facing-an-uncertain-future-what-we-know-about-gen-z-so-far-2/>
- Partanen, E., Kujala, T., Näätänen, R., Liitola, A., Sambeth, A., & Huotilainen, M. (2013). Learning-induced neural plasticity of speech processing before birth. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(37), 15145–15150. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1302159110>
- Pascoe, M. C., de Manincor, M., Tseberja, J., Hallgren, M., Baldwin, P. A., & Parker, A. G. (2021). Psychobiological mechanisms underlying the mood benefits of meditation: A narrative review. *Comprehensive Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 6, Article 100037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpnec.2021.100037>
- Philip, S. T., Thimmapuram, J., Thakur, K., Dayal, N., Patil, Y., Sabbu, K., Surve, S., Patil, P., & Thakur, M. (2025). Heartfulness meditation alters neuroendocrine profiles: A randomized controlled trial on hormones of stress and well-being. *Medicine*, 104(47), Article e45559. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.00000000000045559>
- Pino, O., Di Pietro, S., & Poli, D. (2023). Effect of musical stimulation on placental programming and neurodevelopment outcome of preterm infants: A systematic review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(3), Article 2718. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20032718>
- Polis, R. L., Gussman, D., & Kuo, Y. H. (2015a). Yoga in pregnancy: An examination of maternal and fetal responses to 26 yoga postures. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 126(6), 1237–1241. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AOG.0000000000001137>
- Polis, R. L., Gussman, D., Osial, P., & Kuo, Y. H. (2015b). Safety of yoga in pregnancy. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 125, 21S. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.AOG.0000465322.80077.38>
- Pradhan, B., & Derle, S. G. (2012). Comparison of effect of Gayatri mantra and poem chanting on digit letter substitution task. *Ancient Science of Life*, 32(2), 89–92. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3807963/>
- Provasi, J., Blanc, L., & Carchon, I. (2021). The importance of rhythmic stimulation for preterm infants in the NICU. *Children*, 8(8), Article 660. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children8080660>
- Raman, V., & Thomas, S. (2023). School mental health program in India: Issues and possible practical solutions. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 45(3), 283–288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02537176231165033>

- Rawal, P., Vyas, M., Baghel, A. S., & Kamble, S. (2019). Efficacy of Sattvavajaya Chikitsa in the form of relaxation techniques and Guda Pippalimula Churna in the management of Anidra (insomnia): An open labelled, randomized comparative clinical trial. *AYU (An International Quarterly Journal of Research in Ayurveda)*, 40(2), 89–96. https://doi.org/10.4103/ayu.AYU_91_17
- Roccio, M., Perny, M., Ealy, M., Widmer, H. R., Heller, S., & Senn, P. (2018). Molecular characterization and prospective isolation of human fetal cochlear hair cell progenitors. *Nature Communications*, 9(1), Article 4027. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-06334-7>
- Sarasij, A. (2014). *Bal nirman ki kahaniyan (bhag-1)* [Stories for the righteous development of the children (part-1)]. Yug Nirman Yojana Vistar Trust, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. http://literature.awgp.org/book/bal_nirman_ki_kahaniyan/v1.1
- Saraswat, S., & Sharma, G. (2026). Epigenetics and fetal reprogramming. In R. Garg & P. Lal (Eds.), *Maternal fetal medicine - fetus as a patient: Practical manual* (Chapter 21). Evangel. https://www.jainstationery.com/index.php?route=product/product&manufacturer_id=1567&product_id=13677&page=3
- Sharma, G., & Singh, R. (2022). Efforts to awaken Indian society and pregnant mothers through the movement 'Aao Gadhe Sanskarwan Pidhi - Garbhotsav Sanskar' conducted by Shantikunj: A critical study. *Dev Sanskriti Interdisciplinary International Journal*, 19, 44–53. <https://doi.org/10.36018/dsij.v18i.227>
- Sharma, G., & Singh, R. (2023). *Prachin Bharatiya sanskriti ke mool tatvon ka garbhvati mahila ke sharirik, mansik evam adhyatmik swasthya par padne wale prabhavon ka adhyayan (Shantikunj dwara sanchalit 'Aao Gadhen Sanskarwan Pidhi' andolan ke vishesh sandarbh mein) - Vaiyaktik adhyayan 1* [Effect of the basic elements of ancient Indian culture on the physical, mental and spiritual health of pregnant woman... Case Study 1] [Preprint]. OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/yacbs>
- Sharma, G., & Singh, R. (2025). *Effect of the basic elements of ancient Indian culture on the physical, mental and spiritual health of pregnant woman [with special reference to the 'Aao Gadhe Sanskarwan Pidhi (let's create a well-cultured future generation)' movement coordinated by Shantikunj] - Case study 2* [Preprint]. OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/d2yrp>
- Sharma, G., & Singh, R. (2026a). *Effect of the basic elements of ancient Indian culture on the physical, mental and spiritual health of pregnant woman [with special reference to the 'Aao Gadhe Sanskarwan Pidhi (let's create a well-cultured future generation)' movement coordinated by Shantikunj] - Case study 3* [Preprint]. OSF Preprints. https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/w3x2g_v2
- Sharma, G., & Singh, R. (2026b, February 23). *Impact of an Indian Knowledge Systems based approach on the developmental milestones of a child - a case study*. OSF Preprints. <https://osf.io/u8npw/files/f54be>
- Sharma, G., Singh, R., & Rai, N. (2024a, March 21–22). *Presenting the outreach of 'garbhotsav sanskar' movement aimed at programming foetal brain for a well-cultured generation* [Paper presentation]. International Conference on Scientific Spirituality (SS2024), Dev Sanskriti Vishwavidyalaya, Haridwar, India. OSF Preprints. https://osf.io/preprints/osf/uqxe6_v1

- Sharma, G., Singh, S., & Singh, R. (2024b). *Effect of the basic elements of ancient Indian culture on the physical, mental and spiritual health of pregnant woman [with special reference to the 'Aao Gadhe Sanskarwan Pidhi (let's create a well-cultured future generation)' movement coordinated by Shantikunj] - Case study 1* [Preprint]. OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8hwsf>
- Sharma, N., & Kumar, J. (2025). First-person accounts of Gayatri mantra sadhana practices: An experiential data analysis from practitioners in India. *Journal of Dharma Studies*, 8, 491–515. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42240-025-00205-3>
- Sharma, P. V. (2008). *Charaka-samhita* (Text with English translation, Vols. 1-2). Chaukhambha Orientalia.
- Sharma, S. (2008). *Balakon ka bhavanatmak nirman (bal manovigyan)* [Emotional development of children (child psychology)]. Yug Nirman Yojana, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. http://literature.awgp.org/book/Balakon_Ka_Bhavanatmak_Nirman/v1.1
- Sharma, S. (2010). *Ghar ke vatavaran men svarg ka avataran* [The descent of heaven in the environment of the house]. Yug Nirman Yojana Vistar Trust, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. http://literature.awgp.org/book/ghar_ke_vatavaran_men_svarg_ka_avataran/v1.1
- Sharma, S. (2010a). *Gayatri mahavigyan - sanyukta sanskaran* [Hindi] (Rev. ed.). Yug Nirman Yojana Vistar Trust, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. http://literature.awgp.org/book/Super_Science_of_Gayatri/v2.1
- Sharma, S. (2010b). *Super science of Gayatri* (S. N. Pandya & Shambhudas, Trans.; Rev. ed.). Yug Nirman Yojana Vistar Trust, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. https://www.awgp.org/en/literature/book/Super_Science_of_Gayatri/v1.1
- Sharma, S. (2011). *Grihastha me pravesh se purva usaki jimmedari samajhen* [Before entering the family life, understand its responsibilities]. Yug Nirman Yojana Vistar Trust, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. http://literature.awgp.org/book/grihasth_men_pravesh_se_poorv_usakee_jimmedaree_samajhen/v1.1
- Sharma, S. (2013). *Bharat ki mahan viranganaen* [Great women patriots of India]. Yug Nirman Yojana Vistar Trust, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. https://www.awgp.org/en/literature/book/bharat_ki_mahan_viranganaen/v1.2
- Sharma, S. (2015a). *Karmkand bhaskar (sanskar prakaran)*. Yug Nirman Yojana Vistar Trust, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. https://www.awgp.org/en/literature/book/kram_kand_bhaskar/v1.1
- Sharma, S. (2015b). *Bacchon ka nirman parivar ki prayogshala men* [The development of children in the laboratory of the family]. Yug Nirman Yojana Vistar Trust, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. https://www.awgp.org/en/literature/book/bacho_ka_nirman_pariwar_ki_prayogshala_me/v1.2
- Sharma, S. (Ed.). (1972). *Grihyasutra-sangrah*. Sanskriti Sansthan. <https://ia802909.us.archive.org/11/items/in.ernet.dli.2015.383097/2015.383097.Gruhasutra-Sangraha.pdf>
- Sharma, S., & Pandya, P. (2011). *Suprajanan dvara bhavi pidhi ka navasrujan* [Reconstruction of the future generation through suprajanan]. Yug Nirman Yojana Vistar Trust, Gayatri Tapobhoomi. https://www.awgp.org/en/literature/book/suprajanan_dvara_bhavi_pidhi_ka_navsrujan/v1.2

- Sharma, S., & Sharma, B. D. (2014). *Atharvaveda samhita - saral Hindi bhavarth sahit* [Atharvaveda samhita - with simple Hindi meaning] (Part 1). Yug Nirman Yojna Vistar Trust.
https://vicharkrantibooks.org/productdetail?book_name=HINB0009_ATHARVAVED_SANHITA_BHAG_1_Re2012&product_id=9
- Sharma, S. (Speaker). (n.d.). *Yagya ka gyan-vigyan* (Philosophy and science of yagya) [Audio discourse in Hindi].
<https://sites.google.com/view/adhyatmik-kayakalp/adhyatmik-paddhatiyan-gyan-vigyan/yagya-ka-gyan-vigyan>
- Shetty, N. P., Shetty, J., Hegde, V., Dharme, S. D., & Kv, M. (2024). A machine learning-based clinical decision support system for effective stratification of gestational diabetes mellitus and management through Ayurveda. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine*, 15(6), Article 101051.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaim.2024.101051>
- Shriyan, P., Sudhir, P., van Schayck, O. C. P., & Babu, G. R. (2023). Association of high cortisol levels in pregnancy and altered fetal growth: Results from the MAASTHI, a prospective cohort study, Bengaluru. *The Lancet Regional Health - Southeast Asia*, 14, Article 100196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lansea.2023.100196>
- Shrivastava, V., Batham, L., Mishra, S., & Mishra, A. (2019a). Supportive care in a patient with acute myeloid leukemia through an integrated approach including yagya therapy. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Yagya Research*, 2(2), 20–28.
<https://doi.org/10.36018/ijyr.v2i2.27>
- Shrivastava, V., Batham, L., Mishra, S., & Mishra, A. (2019b). An integrated traditional therapy approach involving yagya therapy in patient with symptoms similar to Crohn's disease. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Yagya Research*, 2(2), 11–19.
<https://doi.org/10.36018/ijyr.v2i2.26>
- Shrivastava, V., Batham, L., Mishra, S., & Mishra, A. (2019c). Management of symptoms associated with obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) and polycystic ovarian disease (PCOD) through an integrated approach including yagya therapy. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Yagya Research*, 2(1), 39–51.
<http://ijyr.dsvv.ac.in/index.php/ijyr/article/view/28>
- Shrivastava, V., Batham, L., Mishra, S., & Mishra, A. (2020b). Application of an integrated approach including yagya therapy for the management of acute pulmonary edema with mild cardiomegaly. *Ayurveda evam Samagra Swasthya Shodhamala*, 2(1), Article 1. <https://sites.google.com/dsvv.ac.in/shodhamala-dahh/asssm21/asssm211>
- Shrivastava, V., Mishra, S., & Mishra, A. (2020a). Exploring the possible applicability of yagya in present time: A review. *Ayurveda evam Samagra Swasthya Shodhamala*, 2(2), Article 1.
<https://sites.google.com/dsvv.ac.in/shodhamala-dahh/asssm22/asssm221>
- Sison, A. J. G., & Redín, D. M. (2023). If MacIntyre ran a business school... how practical wisdom can be developed in management education. *Business Ethics, the Environment & Responsibility*, 32(1), 274–291. <https://doi.org/10.1111/beer.12471>
- Skinner, S. (Ed.). (2022). *Mind the gap – November 2022 edition* [Newsletter]. McKinsey & Company.
<https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/mckinsey/email/genz/2022/11/15/2022-11-15b.html>
- Smith, M., Moran, S., & Walsh, G. (2025). *Gen Alpha unfiltered: A deep dive into the minds, values, and behaviors of the youngest generation* [Report]. GWI.
<https://www.gwi.com/reports/gen-alpha>

- Song, D. (2022). Moving toward a spiritual pedagogy in L2 education: Research, practice, and applications. *Frontiers in Psychology, 13*, Article 978054. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.978054>
- Sumantran, V. N., & Nair, P. P. (2019). Can the vagus nerve serve as biomarker for vata dosha activity? *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine, 10*(2), 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaim.2019.04.003>
- Tadanki, D., Kaza, P. S., Meisinger, E., Syed, A., Johnson, A., Bainbridge, G., Cho, M., Anigbogu, C., & Gupta, G. (2025). Comprehensive review of the impact of maternal stress on fetal development. *Pediatric Discovery, 3*(3), Article e70004. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pdi3.70004>
- Tarsha, M. S., & Narvaez, D. (2023). The evolved nest, oxytocin functioning, and prosocial development. *Frontiers in Psychology, 14*, Article 1113944. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1113944>
- Thompson, R. A. (2014). The development of virtue: A perspective from developmental psychology. In N. E. Snow (Ed.), *Cultivating virtue: Perspectives from philosophy, theology, and psychology*. Oxford Academic. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199967421.003.0012>
- Trottier, M., Erebara, A., & Bozzo, P. (2012). Treating constipation during pregnancy. *Canadian Family Physician, 58*(8), 836–838. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3418980/>
- Turan, A., & Kaya, C. (2023). Effect of maternal cortisol levels on fetal heart rate patterns in primiparous pregnant women in the third trimester. *Revista da Associação Médica Brasileira, 69*(5), Article e20221610. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1806-9282.20221610>
- Ullal-Gupta, S., Vanden Bosch der Nederlanden, C. M., Tichko, P., Lahav, A., & Hannon, E. E. (2013). Linking prenatal experience to the emerging musical mind. *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience, 7*, Article 48. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnsys.2013.00048>
- Vasundhara, V. R., Ramanathan, M., Ghose, S., & Bhavanani, A. B. (2023). Immediate effect of pranava pranayama on fetal and maternal cardiovascular parameters. *International Journal of Yoga, 15*(3), 240–245. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijoy.ijoy_151_22
- Venditti, S., Verdone, L., Reale, A., Vetriani, V., Caserta, M., & Zampieri, M. (2020). Molecules of silence: Effects of meditation on gene expression and epigenetics. *Frontiers in Psychology, 11*, Article 1767. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01767>
- Vickers, M. H. (2014). Early life nutrition, epigenetics and programming of later life disease. *Nutrients, 6*(6), 2165–2178. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu6062165>
- Wadhwa, P. D., Entringer, S., Buss, C., & Lu, M. C. (2011). The contribution of maternal stress to preterm birth: Issues and considerations. *Clinics in Perinatology, 38*(3), 351–384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clp.2011.06.007>
- Wadhwa, P. D., Sandman, C. A., Porto, M., Dunkel-Schetter, C., & Garite, T. J. (1993). The association between prenatal stress and infant birth weight and gestational age at birth: A prospective investigation. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology, 169*(4), 858–865. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378\(93\)90016-C](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9378(93)90016-C)
- Wadhwa, Y., Alghadir, A. H., & Iqbal, Z. A. (2020). Effect of antenatal exercises, including yoga, on the course of labor, delivery and pregnancy: A retrospective study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 17*(15), Article 5274. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17155274>

- Wiley, K. S., Camilo, C., Gouveia, G., Euclides, V., Panter-Brick, C., Matijasevich, A., Ferraro, A. A., Fraccolli, L. A., Chiesa, A. M., Miguel, E. C., Polanczyk, G. V., & Brentani, H. (2023). Maternal distress, DNA methylation, and fetal programming of stress physiology in Brazilian mother-infant pairs. *Developmental Psychobiology*, 65(1), Article e22352. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dev.22352>
- Xu, X., Liu, Z., Gong, S., & Wu, Y. (2022). The relationship between empathy and attachment in children and adolescents: Three-level meta-analyses. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(3), Article 1391. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19031391>
- Zhu, P., Tao, F., Hao, J., Sun, Y., & Jiang, X. (2010). Prenatal life events stress: Implications for preterm birth and infant birthweight. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 203(1), 34.e1–34.e8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2010.02.023>
- Zhu, Z., Cao, F., & Li, X. (2019). Epigenetic programming and fetal metabolic programming. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 10, Article 764. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2019.00764>
- Zubler, J. M., Wiggins, L. D., Macias, M. M., Whitaker, T. M., Shaw, J. S., Squires, J. K., Pajek, J. A., Wolf, R. B., Slaughter, K. S., Broughton, A. S., Gerndt, K. L., Mlodoch, B. J., & Lipkin, P. H. (2022). Evidence-informed milestones for developmental surveillance tools. *Pediatrics*, 149(3), Article e2021052138. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2021-052138>
- Zuccarello, D., Sorrentino, U., Brasson, V., et al. (2022). Epigenetics of pregnancy: Looking beyond the DNA code. *Journal of Assisted Reproduction and Genetics*, 39, 801–816. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10815-022-02451-x>

Annexure-1 (Registration Form)

गर्भोत्सव संस्कार

आओ गढ़े
संस्कारवान
पीढ़ी

गर्भवती महिला एवं परिवार के सदस्यों का पूर्ण परिचय

गर्भवती महिला का नाम उपनाम

जाति धर्म पति का नाम

जन्म तिथि विवाह तिथि दीक्षा तिथि

पता जिला

प्रान्त पिनकोड

मोबाइल/ व्हाट्सऐप ई-मेल

भाषा शिक्षा व्यवसाय

प्रसव (Delivery) की 1) अनुमानित तिथि - 2) वास्तविक तिथि -

प्रसव पीड़ा (Labour pain) की अवधि -

प्रसव (Delivery) के प्रकार - (प्राकृतिक) Normal / (सिजेरियन) Cesarean -

जन्म लिए बच्चे की जन्म तिथि बच्चे का नाम

बच्चों का विवरण

क्र.	नाम	लिंग	जन्म तिथि	शिक्षा	कराए गए संस्कारों के नाम
1					
2					
3					

परिवार का विवरण

क्र.	नाम	जन्म तिथि	विवाह तिथि	शिक्षा	सम्बन्ध
1					
2					
3					

अन्य विवरण

.....

जाँच और सत्यापित

जाँच और सत्यापित

*गर्भवती नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर *क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर *जनपदीय समन्वयक नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर *प्रांतीय समन्वयक नाम, हस्ताक्षर एवं मोहर *प्रधान अन्वेषक नाम, हस्ताक्षर एवं मोहर

Aao Gadhein Sanskarvan Peedhi
Let's Build a Well-Cultured Future Generation
Garbhotsav Sanskar

Complete Details of the Pregnant Woman and Family Members

Name of the Pregnant Woman: Surname

Caste Religion Husband's Name

Date of Birth Date of Marriage Date of Initiation (Deeksha)

Address

District State Pin Code

Mobile/WhatsApp Email

Language Education Occupation

Date of Delivery 1) Estimated 2) Actual

Duration of Labor Pain

Type of Delivery – Normal / Cesarean

Date of Birth of the newborn child Name of the child

Details of Children

S.No.	Name	Gender	Date of Birth	Education	Names of Sacramental rites (संस्कार) performed
1					
2					
3					

Family Details

S.No.	Name	Date of Birth	Date of Marriage	Education	Relationship
1					
2					
3					

Other Details

.....

.....

Checked and Verified Checked and Verified

.....

Pregnant Woman Field Volunteer District Coordinator State Coordinator Principal Investigator
Name & Signature Name & Signature Name & Signature Name, Signature & Seal Name, Signature & Seal

Annexure-2 (Consent Form)

सहमति प्रपत्र

(गर्भवती महिला / नए प्रतिभागी हेतु)

मुझे शोधकर्ता द्वारा, जिस उद्देश्य के लिए मुझे शोधकार्य में भाग लेना है, उसके फायदे व नुकसान बता दिए गए हैं - मुझे ज्ञात है कि इसमें मुझे गर्भ संस्कार, आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन, गर्भावस्था में आहार, गर्भ संवाद, योगासन, प्राणायाम, ध्यान करवाया जायेगा। मुझे ज्ञात है कि इस शोधकार्य के अंतर्गत सम्पूर्ण स्वास्थ्य से सम्बन्धित प्रश्नावली, आदर्श दिनचर्या चार्ट, बच्चे का शारीरिक मानसिक विकास चार्ट, आदि भरवाए जाएंगे।

मैं बिना किसी दबाव के, अपनी इच्छानुसार:

(1) इस शोधकार्य में भाग लेने के लिए सहमत हूँ। इस शोधकार्य के लिए सभी प्रकार के परीक्षण, जो मानव जाति के कल्याण के लिए ज्ञान प्रदान करते हैं, के लिए सहमत हूँ।

(2) इस शोधकार्य के लिए मैं गर्भ संस्कार करवाने, आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन, गर्भावस्था में आहार, गर्भ संवाद, योगासन, प्राणायाम, ध्यान करने के लिए सहमत हूँ। इस शोधकार्य के लिए सम्पूर्ण स्वास्थ्य से सम्बन्धित प्रश्नावली, आदर्श दिनचर्या चार्ट, बच्चे को शारीरिक मानसिक विकास चार्ट, जो मुझे भरने हैं, उसके लिए मैं सहमत हूँ।

मेरी सहमति प्रत्यक्ष रूप से किसी भी व्यक्तिगत जानकारी के खुलासे के लिए नहीं है। मेरे आंकड़ों से प्राप्त व्यक्तिगत जानकारी के खुलासे के लिए मेरी अगली अनुमति अनिवार्य है।

मुझे सूचित किया जा चुका है कि आओ गढ़े संस्कारवान पीढ़ी कार्यालय, शान्तिकुञ्ज, हरिद्वार, उत्तराखण्ड एवं शोधार्थी (मुख्य शोधार्थी - डॉ. गायत्री शर्मा एवं सहायक शोधार्थी - श्रीमती ऋतु सिंह) मेरे ऊपर की जाने वाली शोध एवं उससे प्राप्त आंकड़ों से किसी भी प्रकार का लाभ लेने से पूर्व, इस हेतु मेरी सहमति अवश्य लेंगे। चिकित्सकीय, वैज्ञानिक, शैक्षणिक तथा शोधपरक कार्यों में उपयोग हेतु मैं इस शोध के प्रारम्भ, दौरान एवं अंत में अपनी फोटोग्राफी एवं वीडियोग्राफी करने की अनुमति देती हूँ। मैं इस बात से सहमत हूँ कि बिना मेरी व्यक्तिगत जानकारी का खुलासा किए, इस डाटा (आंकड़ों, आदि) को शोधकार्य हेतु प्रयुक्त किया जा सकता है, एवं इस डाटा (आंकड़ों, आदि) और इससे प्राप्त निष्कर्षों को शोध जर्नल एवं कॉन्फ्रेंस में प्रस्तुत किया जा सकता है।

.....
प्रतिभागी का नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर

.....
गवाह का नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर

.....
क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता का नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर

कार्यालय के उपयोग हेतु

क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता (नाम) _____ से यह सहमति प्रपत्र प्राप्त किया।

.....
प्रांतीय समन्वयक का नाम, हस्ताक्षर एवं मोहर

प्रांतीय समन्वयक (नाम) _____ से यह सहमति प्रपत्र प्राप्त किया।

.....
सहायक शोधार्थी का नाम, हस्ताक्षर एवं मोहर

.....
मुख्य शोधार्थी का नाम, हस्ताक्षर एवं मोहर

Consent Form
(For Pregnant Woman / New Participant)

The researcher has explained to me the purpose for which I am to participate in this research study, as well as its benefits and risks. I am aware that during this study, I will be guided to perform Garbh Sanskar (prenatal sacramental rite), follow an ideal daily routine, maintain a proper diet during pregnancy, and practice Garbh Samvad (womb conversation), Yoga postures, Pranayama, and Meditation, etc. I am aware that under this research study, I will be required to fill out a comprehensive health-related questionnaire, an ideal daily routine chart, the child's physical and mental development chart, etc.

Without any pressure and of my own free will:

(1) I agree to participate in this research study. I consent to all types of tests for this research study that provide knowledge for the welfare of mankind.

(2) For this research study, I agree to undergo Garbh Sanskar, follow an ideal daily routine, maintain a proper diet during pregnancy, and practice Garbh Samvad, Yoga postures, Pranayama, and Meditation, etc. I agree to fill out the comprehensive health-related questionnaire, the ideal daily routine chart, and the child's physical and mental development chart required for this research study.

My consent does not implicitly allow the disclosure of any personal information. My further prior permission is mandatory for the disclosure of any personal information obtained from my data.

I have been informed that the 'Aao Gadhein Sanskarvan Peedhi' Office, Shantikunj, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, and the researchers (Principal Investigator - Dr. Gayatri Sharma and Co-Investigator - Mrs. Ritu Singh) will definitely seek my consent before deriving any kind of benefit from the research conducted on me and the data obtained from it. I grant permission for my photography and videography at the beginning, during, and at the end of this research for use in medical, scientific, educational, and research purposes. I agree that without disclosing my personal information, this data (statistics, etc.) can be used for research work, and this data and the conclusions derived from it may be presented in research journals and conferences.

Name & Signature of Participant	Name & Signature of Witness	Name & Signature of Field Worker
For Office Use		

Received this consent form from Field Worker (Name)

.....
Name, Sign, Seal of State Coordinator

Received this consent form from the State Coordinator (Name)

.....
Name, Signature, and Seal
of Co-Investigator

.....
Name, Signature, and Seal
of Principal Investigator

Annexure-3 (Participant Information Sheet)

संस्थान का नाम / पता - आओ गढ़ें संस्कारवान पीढ़ी कार्यालय, शांतिकुंज, हरिद्वार, उत्तराखंड

प्रतिभागी सूचना पत्रक
(नए प्रतिभागी हेतु)

"Research Topic" - गर्भवती महिला एवं शिशु के शारीरिक, मानसिक एवं आध्यात्मिक स्वास्थ्य पर प्राचीन भारतीय संस्कृति के मूल तत्वों पर आधारित आदर्श दिनचर्या का प्रभाव

मुख्य शोधार्थी : डॉ. गायत्री शर्मा
सहायक शोधार्थी - श्रीमती ऋतु सिंह

शोध कार्य का परिचय

आज बच्चों के नैतिक और भावनात्मक मूल्य गिर जाने के कारण उनके चिंतन, चरित्र और व्यवहार में उत्कृष्टता का अभाव दिखाई देता है। यही कारण है कि आज के समय में बच्चे क्रोधी, आलसी, प्रमादी, अपराधी प्रवृत्ति के, चिड़चिड़े, झगड़ालू, असहिष्णु, आवेशग्रस्त, मादक वस्तुओं एवं इलेक्ट्रॉनिक उपकरणों की लतों से ग्रसित, माता पिता एवं समाज के लिए समस्या बनते जा रहे हैं।

प्राचीन समय में भारतीय संस्कृति के अंतर्गत बताए गए नियमों का पालन करते हुए माता पिता संस्कारित बच्चों को जन्म देते थे। प्राचीन भारतीय संस्कृति के मूल तत्वों के अंतर्गत गर्भ संस्कार (पुंसवन, सीमंतोन्नयन एवं गर्भाधान संस्कारों का समन्वित स्वरूप) के माध्यम से, आदर्श दिनचर्या के पालन, योग व्यायाम, प्राणायाम, ध्यान, गर्भ संवाद, संतुलित संस्कारित सात्विक भोजन, स्वाध्याय, सत्संग, सकारात्मक चिंतन द्वारा गर्भ से ही बच्चे के शारीरिक, मानसिक एवं आध्यात्मिक विकास की नींव डाल दी जाती थी, जिसके कारण गर्भस्थ शिशु के अचेतन मस्तिष्क पर उत्कृष्ट संस्कारों के रूप में स्थाई रूप से सूक्ष्म छाप पड़ जाती थी, और फलस्वरूप एक सुसंस्कारित मनचाही संतान को जन्म दिया जाता था।

अतः, वर्तमान शोध में, उपरोक्त वर्णित प्राचीन भारतीय संस्कृति के मूल तत्वों के गर्भवती महिला के शारीरिक, मानसिक एवं आध्यात्मिक स्वास्थ्य, एवं उसकी भावी संतान (गर्भ से ले कर जन्म होने के उपरांत तक) के समग्र विकास पर पड़ने वाले प्रभावों का अध्ययन किया जाएगा।

आपको क्या करना है ?

प्रस्तुत शोध का उद्देश्य गर्भवती महिला द्वारा गर्भ संस्कार में बताई गयी आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के उपरांत उनके एवं शिशु के शारीरिक, मानसिक और आध्यात्मिक स्वास्थ्य पर पड़ने वाले प्रभाव का अध्ययन करना है।

इस हेतु आपसे -

- 1) प्रशिक्षित क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता (या छोटे समूह) द्वारा गर्भ संस्कार सम्पन्न करवाया जाएगा। इस संदर्भ में आपसे संपर्क करने वाली क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता की जानकारी आपको दी जाएगी।
- 2) कार्यकर्ता द्वारा आपसे पंजीयन फॉर्म भरवाया जाएगा।
- 3) संस्कार में गर्भवती महिला, उनके पति एवं परिवार के सदस्यों से संकल्प करवाया जाएगा।
- 4) पांच विषयों पर प्रशिक्षण दिया जाएगा, जो जीवन शैली पर सकारात्मक प्रभाव डालते हैं। विषय निम्नानुसार हैं -

- गर्भ का ज्ञान विज्ञान
- आदर्श दिनचर्या
- आहार (संतुलित, सात्विक, संस्कारित)
- गर्भावस्था में आसन, प्राणायाम, ध्यान
- गर्भ संवाद

- 5) आदर्श दिनचर्या चार्ट दिया जाएगा जिसको आपको हर महीने भर कर कार्यकर्ता को देना होगा।

- 6) आपको "माँ की पाठशाला" ग्रुप से जोड़ दिया जाएगा जिससे कि आप निरंतर सम्पर्क में बनी रह कर उसका लाभ उठा सकें। इस ग्रुप के द्वारा नियमित दिनचर्या पालन करने हेतु सलाह दी जाएगी एवं नियमित योगासन, प्राणायाम, ध्यान, आदि का अभ्यास भी कराया जाएगा।
- 7) बच्चे के जन्म के बाद बच्चे की शारीरिक मानसिक विकास तालिका भी भरवाई जाएगी।
- 8) बच्चे के विकास क्रम का वीडियो तथा चित्र भी मंगवाया जाएगा।

प्राचीन भारतीय संस्कृति के मूल तत्वों पर आधारित आदर्श दिनचर्या, योगासन, प्राणायाम, ध्यान, आहार, गर्भ संवाद का प्रभाव गर्भवती महिला एवं शिशु पर क्या पड़ा, इसका अध्ययन प्रश्नावली के माध्यम से किया जाएगा, जो कि कार्यकर्ता आपसे भरवाएंगे। साथ ही, आपके पारिवारिक वातावरण में क्या सकारात्मक परिवर्तन आया, यह भी देखा जाएगा।

आपके द्वारा दी गई समस्त जानकारी क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता द्वारा प्रांतीय समन्वयक (नाम) (पंजीयन संख्या) को दी जाएगी, एवं तदुपरांत प्रांतीय समन्वयक द्वारा वह जानकारी मुख्य शोधार्थी एवं सहायक शोधार्थी को दे दी जाएगी।

शोध कार्य से मिलने वाले सम्भावित फ़ायदे -

- गर्भवती एवं गर्भस्थ शिशु का शारीरिक, मानसिक एवं आध्यात्मिक विकास होगा।
- पति का सहयोग मिलेगा।
- परिवार में आपसी सामंजस्य अच्छा होगा।
- आपके इस कार्य में भाग लेने से भविष्य में होने वाले वैज्ञानिक अन्वेषकों को प्रेरणा एवं सहायता मिलेगी।
- भावी पीढ़ी के निर्माण एवं उन्हें सुसंस्कारित बनाने में सहायता मिलेगी।

इस कार्य से सम्बन्धित खतरे -

इस कार्य में साधारणतया कोई भी दुष्प्रभाव नहीं देखा गया है। प्रारम्भिक दिनों में, पूर्व की दिनचर्या के अभ्यास के कारण, आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने में कठिनाई, असुविधा तथा थकान हो सकती है।

अभिलेखों की गोपनीयता -

प्रतिभागी की निजी जानकारी को पूर्णतया गोपनीय रखा जाएगा।

दुर्घटना द्वारा असमय मृत्यु हो जाने पर मिलने वाला मुआवजा -
लागू नहीं होता।

कार्य को छोड़कर जाने की स्वतंत्रता -

प्रतिभागी कभी भी इस कार्य को छोड़ सकता है। इस हेतु उसे न तो कोई कारण देना होगा और न ही उस पर कोई हर्जाना लगाया जाएगा।

प्रतिभागी का कथन -

मुझे उपरोक्त सभी बातें बता दी गई हैं।

प्रतिभागी का नाम: प्रतिभागी का हस्ताक्षर: दिनांक:

प्रतिभागी के माता/पिता/संरक्षक का नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर:
(यदि प्रतिभागी उपरोक्त जानकारी को समझने अथवा हस्ताक्षर करने में समर्थ न हो)

प्रतिभागी से संबंध: दिनांक:

शोधकर्ता का कथन -

मैंने प्रतिभागी/ संरक्षक/ अभिभावक (जिन्होंने हस्ताक्षर किए हैं) को उनके समझने योग्य भाषा में शोध कार्य की पूरी विधि, फायदे व खतरों के बारे में अवगत करा दिया है।

गवाह के हस्ताक्षर:

गवाह का नाम:

दिनांक:

क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता के हस्ताक्षर:

क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता का नाम:

दिनांक:

कार्यालय के उपयोग हेतु

क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता (नाम:) से यह प्रतिभागी सूचना पत्रक प्राप्त किया।

प्रांतीय समन्वयक के हस्ताक्षर:

प्रांतीय समन्वयक का नाम:

दिनांक:

प्रांतीय समन्वयक (नाम:) से यह प्रतिभागी सूचना पत्रक प्राप्त किया।

सहायक शोधार्थी के हस्ताक्षर:

सहायक शोधार्थी का नाम:

दिनांक:

मुख्य शोधार्थी के हस्ताक्षर:

मुख्य शोधार्थी का नाम:

दिनांक:

Name / Address of the Institution:

'Aao Gadhein Sanskarvan Peedhi' Office, Shantikunj, Haridwar, Uttarakhand

Participant Information Sheet

(For New Participant)

Research Topic: The Impact of an Ideal Daily Routine Based on the Core Elements of Ancient Indian Culture on the Physical, Mental, and Spiritual Health of the Pregnant Woman and Infant

Principal Investigator: Dr. Gayatri Sharma

Co-Investigator: Mrs. Ritu Singh

Introduction to the Research Study

Today, due to the decline in the moral and emotional values of children, there is a visible lack of excellence in their thinking, character, and behavior. This is why in modern times, children are increasingly becoming a problem for their parents and society, exhibiting traits such as anger, laziness, negligence, criminal tendencies, irritability, quarrelsomeness, intolerance, impulsiveness, and addiction to intoxicants and electronic devices.

In ancient times, by following the rules prescribed within Indian culture, parents gave birth to well-cultured (sanskarit) children. Under the core elements of ancient Indian culture, the foundation for the child's physical, mental, and spiritual development was laid from the womb itself. This was done through Garbh Sanskar (integration of Punsavan, Simantonnayana and Garbhadhan sacrament rites), adhering to an ideal daily routine, practicing yoga exercises, pranayama, meditation, womb conversation (Garbh Samvad), consuming a balanced, pure (Sattvic), and virtuous (Sanskarit) diet, engaging in self-study (Swadhyaya), keeping righteous company (Satsang), and maintaining positive thinking. As a result, righteous values were permanently and subtly imprinted on the unconscious mind of the fetus, leading to the birth of a desired well-cultured child.

Therefore, in the present research, the effects of the aforementioned core elements of ancient Indian culture on the physical, mental, and spiritual health of the pregnant woman and the holistic development of her future child (from the womb until after birth) will be studied.

What are you expected to do?

The objective of this research is to study the effect on the physical, mental, and spiritual health of the pregnant woman and the infant, after the pregnant woman follows the ideal daily routine prescribed in Garbh Sanskar.

For this purpose, you will be required to:

1. Participate in the Garbh Sanskar sacramental rite conducted by a trained field volunteer (or by a small group). You will be provided with the details of the field volunteer who will contact you regarding this.
2. Fill out a registration form provided by the field volunteer.
3. Take a pledge (Sankalp) along with your husband and family members during the sacramental rite.

4. Receive training on five subjects that positively impact your lifestyle. The subjects are as follows:

- * The Science and Knowledge of the Womb
- * Ideal Daily Routine
- * Diet (Balanced, Pure (Sattvic), Virtuous (Sanskrit))
- * Asanas, Pranayama, and Meditation during Pregnancy
- * Womb Conversation (Garbh Samvad)

5. Maintain an Ideal Daily Routine Chart, which you must fill out every month and hand over to the field volunteer.

6. Join the "Maa Ki Pathshala" (Mother's School) group so you can stay in continuous contact and benefit from it. Through this group, advice will be given to follow a regular daily routine, and regular practice of yoga, pranayama, meditation, etc., will be facilitated.

7. Fill out the child's physical and mental development chart after the child's birth.

8. Provide videos and pictures of the child's developmental milestones.

The impact of the ideal daily routine, yoga asanas, pranayama, meditation, proper diet, and womb conversation - based on the core elements of ancient Indian culture - on the pregnant woman and the infant will be studied through questionnaires, which the field volunteer will ask you to fill out. Additionally, any positive changes in your family environment will also be observed.

All the information provided by you will be submitted by the field volunteer to the State Coordinator (Name) (Registration Number), and subsequently, the State Coordinator will forward that information to the Principal Investigator and Co-Investigator.

Potential Benefits of the Research Study

- * Physical, mental, and spiritual development of the pregnant woman and the fetus.
- * Support from your husband.
- * Improved mutual harmony within the family.
- * Your participation in this study will inspire and assist future scientific researchers.
- * It will help in the righteous development of the future generation and instilling good values in them.

Risks Associated with this Study

Generally, no adverse effects have been observed in this study. In the initial days, due to the habit of your previous routine, you may experience difficulty, discomfort, and fatigue in following the ideal daily routine.

Confidentiality of Records

The participant's personal information will be kept completely confidential.

Compensation in Case of Premature Death due to Accident

Not applicable.

Freedom to Withdraw from the Study

The participant can withdraw from this study at any time. For this, she will neither have to provide a reason nor will any penalty be imposed on her.

Participant's Statement

I have been provided all the above-mentioned information.

Participant's Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Name and Signature of Participant's Parent/Guardian: _____
(If the participant is unable to understand the above information or sign)

Relationship with Participant: _____ Date: _____

Researcher's Statement

I have informed the participant/guardian/parent (who has signed) about the complete procedure, benefits, and risks of the research study in a language they can understand.

Witness's Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Field Volunteer's Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

For Office Use

Received this participant information sheet from Field Volunteer (Name:).

State Coordinator's Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Received this participant information sheet from the State Coordinator (Name:).

Co-Investigator's Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Principal Investigator's Name: _____ Signature: _____ Date: _____

Annexure-5 (Questionnaire – Pregnant Woman)

प्रश्नावली - गर्भवती महिला Questionnaire – Pregnant Woman

वे प्रश्न जो गर्भवती महिला से पूछे गए उनके समग्र स्वास्थ्य (शारीरिक, मानसिक, सामाजिक एवं आध्यात्मिक) के बारे में, भारतीय ज्ञान प्रणाली पर आधारित आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व एवं उपरांत

Questions that were asked to the pregnant woman about her overall health status (physical, mental, social, and spiritual), before and after following the Indian Knowledge Systems based ideal/righteous daily routine.

S. No.	शारीरिक स्वास्थ्य - आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व एवं उपरांत	Physical health before/after following the ideal routine	Before following Ideal routine आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व			After following Ideal routine आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के उपरांत		
			Yes हाँ	Sometime कभी-कभी	No नहीं	Yes हाँ	Sometime कभी-कभी	No नहीं
1.	क्या आप सूर्योदय से पूर्व उठती थीं/हैं?	Did/Do you wake up before sunrise?						
2.	क्या आप दैनिक दिनचर्या की कार्ययोजना बनाती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you prepare the schedule for the day in the morning?						
3.	क्या आपको भूख लगती थी /है? क्या आपको भोजन करने की इच्छा होती थी /है?	Did/Do you feel hungry? Did/Do you feel like taking food?						
4.	क्या आप दिन भर में आठ से नौ गिलास पानी पीती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you drink 8 to 9 glasses of water during the day?						
5.	क्या आप उषापान करने का अभ्यास नियमित करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you do Ushapaan (drink water in the early morning) regularly?						
6.	क्या आप संगीत के साथ योगासन करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you do yogasana with music?						
7.	क्या आप दैनिक प्रातः कार्य जैसे स्नान, शौच आदि संगीत के साथ करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you do daily morning chores like taking bath, toilet, etc. along with music?						
8.	क्या आप सूक्ष्म नाश्ता करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you take light breakfast?						
9.	क्या आप अंकुरित का सेवन करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you eat sprouts?						
10.	क्या आप रंगबिरंगी सब्जी एवं फलों का सेवन करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you consume multi-colored fruits and vegetables?						
11.	क्या आप नशीले पदार्थ का सेवन करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you take any intoxicating substance?						
12.	क्या आप नियमित टहलने जाती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you go for a walk regularly?						
13.	क्या आप नियमित योगासन करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you do yogasan regularly?						
14.	क्या आप प्राणायाम संवाद के साथ करती थीं /हैं?	Did/ Do you do pranayama along with womb conversation?						
15.	क्या आप सीढ़ियाँ आसानी से चढ़ लेती थीं /हैं?	Were/Are you able to climb stairs comfortably?						
16.	क्या आप घर के हल्के फुल्के कार्य जैसे खाना बनाना, डस्टिंग करना, कपड़े तह लगाना आदि कर लेती थीं /हैं?	Were/Are you able to do light household chores such as cooking, dusting, folding clothes, etc.?						
17.	क्या आप घर के भारी कार्य जैसे झाड़-पोंछा लगाना, हाथ से कपड़े	Were/Are you able to do heavy household chores such as						

	धोना आदि कर लेती थीं / हैं?	brooming, mopping, washing clothes by hand, etc.?						
18	क्या आप मध्यकालीन शयन करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you take an afternoon nap?						
19	क्या आप मध्यकालीन नाश्ता करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you take snacks at noon?						
20	क्या आपको सर्दी-जुखाम बार-बार होता था / है?	Did/Do you catch cold and cough frequently?						
21	क्या उल्टी होती थी / है?	Did/Do you vomit?						
22	क्या आप भोजन से पूर्व हाथ धोती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you wash your hands before taking meal?						
23	क्या आप रात्रिकालीन हल्का भोजन करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you take a light meal at night?						
24	क्या आप सायंकालीन टहलती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you go for a walk in the evening?						
25	क्या आप दूध में हल्दी एवं शहद डाल कर ग्रहण करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you add turmeric and honey to milk before consuming it?						
26	क्या आप माँसाहार करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you consume non-vegetarian food?						
27	क्या आप शारीरिक स्वच्छता जैसे नियमित स्नान, शयन के पूर्व ब्रश करना आदि पर ध्यान देती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you maintain personal hygiene such as bathing regularly, brushing your teeth before sleep, etc.?						
28	क्या आप अपने घर के रसोई घर, टॉयलेट, नालियाँ, कूड़ेदान आदि की स्वच्छता पर ध्यान देती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you maintain the hygiene and cleanliness of the kitchen, toilet, drains, dustbin, etc. of your house?						
29	क्या आपके घर में आपके द्वारा मोबाइल, लैपटॉप, तथा अन्य डिजिटल गजेट्स का प्रयोग अब भी किया जाता था / है?	Did/Do you still use mobile, laptop, and any other digital gadgets in your house?						
30	क्या आपके घर में धूमपान, तम्बाकू, शराब या अन्य नशीले पदार्थों का प्रयोग किया जा रहा था / है?	Was/Is cigarette, tobacco, alcohol or any other intoxicating substance, still being used in your house?						

मानसिक स्वास्थ्य - आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व एवं उपरांत								
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S. No.	मानसिक स्वास्थ्य - आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व एवं उपरांत	Mental health before/after following the ideal routine	Before following Ideal routine आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व			After following Ideal routine आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के उपरांत		
			Yes हाँ	Sometime कभी-कभी	No नहीं	Yes हाँ	Sometime कभी-कभी	No नहीं
1.	क्या दैनिक घरेलू प्रबंधन में कठिनाइयाँ होती थी / हैं?	Did/Do you face any problems in daily household management?						
2.	क्या नींद संबंधित कोई बीमारी थी / है?	Did/Do you have any disease related to sleep?						
3.	क्या आप थकान, ऊर्जाहीन अनुभव करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you feel tired and lack of energy?						
4.	क्या उदास, अवसादग्रस्त अवस्थाएँ बनी रहती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do gloomy and depressed states persist?						
5.	क्या आपके द्वारा लड़ाई-झगड़ा, क्रोध, तनाव, तेज आवाज, गाली-गलौज, कलह-क्लेश की भावना का वातावरण बनता था / है?	Did/Do you create an environment of quarrel, anger, stress, loud voice, abuse, distress?						
6.	क्या आप संतुष्ट थीं / हैं? (अ) अपने स्वास्थ्य से (ब) रिश्तों से (स) रहन-सहन की स्थिति से	Were/Are you satisfied? (a) From your health (b) From your relations (c) from your lifestyle						
7.	क्या आप प्रसन्न रहती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you feel happy?						

8.	क्या आप प्रवचन सुनकर बच्चे से बातें करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you listen to spiritual discourses/sermons and do womb conversation?						
9.	मैं शांत और संतुलित इंसान थीं / हूँ।	I was/am a calm and balanced person.						
10.	क्या आप स्वाध्याय करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you do Swadhyaya (Reading enlightening literature and contemplating on it)?						
11.	क्या आप ध्यान संवाद के साथ करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you meditate along with womb conversation?						
12.	क्या आप रात्रि शयन से पूर्व पूरे दिन के कार्य की समीक्षा करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you do a review of the entire day's activities before going to sleep at night?						
13.	क्या आप शयन से पूर्व गीत सुनकर शयन करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you listen to soothing songs before going to sleep at night?						
14.	क्या आप प्रेरणादायक गीत (प्रज्ञा गीत) के साथ संवाद करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you do womb conversation along with inspirational songs (Pragya Geet)?						
15.	क्या आप घर के कार्य संगीत के साथ करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you do household chores along with music?						
16.	क्या आप भोजन संगीत/मंत्र के साथ ग्रहण करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you take food along with music/mantra?						
17.	क्या आप कहानी के माध्यम से संवाद करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you do womb conversation through stories?						
18.	क्या आप वाद्ययंत्र पर ध्यान करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you meditate upon musical instrument?						

Social and familial relations before/after following the ideal routine								
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S. No.	सामाजिक एवं पारिवारिक संबंध - आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व एवं उपरांत	Social and familial relations before/after following the ideal routine	Before following Ideal routine आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व			After following Ideal routine आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के उपरांत		
			Yes हाँ	Sometime कभी-कभी	No नहीं	Yes हाँ	Sometime कभी-कभी	No नहीं
1.	क्या आप और आपके पति के बीच सामंजस्य अच्छा था / है?	Was/Is there harmony between you and your husband?						
2.	क्या आप और आपके परिवार के बीच सामंजस्य अच्छा था / है?	Was/Is there harmony between you and your family?						
3.	क्या आप चारों ओर ऐसे लोगों से घिरी रहती थीं / हैं जिन पर आप भरोसा करती हैं?	Were /Are you surrounded by people whom you trust?						
4.	क्या समस्याओं को संवाद द्वारा निपटाने में सक्षम थीं / हैं?	Were/Are you capable of solving problems through conversations?						
5.	क्या आपके पास कम से कम एक अच्छा दोस्त था / है जिस पर आप भरोसा कर सकती हैं?	Did/Do you have at least one friend whom you can trust?						
6.	क्या आपके घर में लड़ाई-झगड़ा, क्रोध, तनाव, तेज आवाज, गाली-गलौज, कलह-क्लेश का वातावरण बना रहता था / है?	Did/Does an environment of quarrel, anger, stress, loud voice, abuse, distress persist in your house?						
7.	क्या आप गर्भस्थ शिशु से बातें करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you talk to the child in the womb?						
8.	क्या आपके परिवार के सदस्य गर्भस्थ शिशु से बातें करते थे / हैं?	Did/Do your family members talk to the child in the womb?						
9.	क्या आप परिवार के सदस्यों की सेवा सहयोग करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you serve your family members and cooperate with them?						
10.	क्या आप पड़ोसी के दुःख-दर्द में सहयोग करती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you help and support your neighbors in their grief?						
11.	क्या आप समाज के लिए अपनी कमाई का एक अंश निकालती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you donate a part of your income for the welfare of society?						
12.	क्या समाज को ऊँचा उठाने के लिए कुछ समय देती थीं / हैं?	Did/Do you donate some time for the upliftment of society?						

13	क्या परिवार के सदस्य आपके गृह कार्य में आपका सहयोग करते थे /हैं?	Did/Do your family members help you with your household chores?						
14	क्या संकट की स्थिति में, आपके परिवार से वह समर्थन प्राप्त होगा जिसकी आपको आवश्यकता थी /है?	In times of crisis, did/do you get the support that you need from your family members?						
15	क्या संकट की स्थिति में, आपके दोस्तों से वह समर्थन प्राप्त होगा जिसकी आपको आवश्यकता थी /है?	In times of crisis, did/do you get the support that you need from your friends?						
16	क्या संकट की स्थिति में, आपके पड़ोसी से वह समर्थन प्राप्त होगा जिसकी आपको आवश्यकता थी /है?	In times of crisis, did/do you get the support that you need from your neighbors?						
17	क्या शाम के समय सभी परिवार के सदस्य मिलकर आरती, पूजा, स्वाध्याय, भोजन आदि समूह में करते थे /हैं?	In the evening, did/do all the family members perform aarti and worship (pooja), do swadhyaya (reading enlightening literature and contemplating on it), take food, etc. collectively?						
18	क्या आप बलिवेश्व यज्ञ करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you do Balivaishva Yagya (sacred ritual of offering a small part of cooked meal to sacred fire before taking the meal)						

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S. No.	आध्यात्मिक स्वास्थ्य - आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व एवं उपरांत	Spiritual health before/after following the ideal routine	Before following Ideal routine आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के पूर्व			After following Ideal routine आदर्श दिनचर्या का पालन करने के उपरांत		
			Yes हाँ	Sometime कभी-कभी	No नहीं	Yes हाँ	Sometime कभी-कभी	No नहीं
1.	क्या आप जागरण के पश्चात प्रार्थना करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you do prayer after waking up?						
2.	क्या आप आत्मबोध की साधना करती थीं /हैं? (प्रातः जागरण के बाद एक दिन का जीवन मानते हुए उसके सदुपयोग की योजना)	Did/Do you do Atma-Bodh Sadhana? (immediately after waking up, considering the day ahead as a life for one day, making plan for its proper/righteous utilization)?						
3.	क्या आप तत्त्वबोध (रात्रि में शयन से पूर्व दिन भर के अच्छे-बुरे कार्यों/विचारों की समीक्षा) की साधना करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you do Tatva-Bodh Sadhana? (before going to sleep at night, doing a review of your good/bad deeds/thoughts during the entire day)						
4.	क्या आप नियमित गायत्री मंत्र/ अन्य मंत्र का जप करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you recite Gayatri Mantra or any other mantra regularly?						
5.	क्या आप अध्ययन (आत्म समीक्षा, आत्म सुधार, आत्म निर्माण, आत्म विकास) करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you do introspection (including self-analysis, self-refinement, self-development, self-expansion)?						
6.	क्या आप नियमित यज्ञ करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you perform yagya (sacred ritual of offering oblations in the sacred fire) regularly?						
7.	क्या आप स्वाध्याय (अच्छी पुस्तकों का अध्ययन) करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you do swadhyaya (reading enlightening literature and contemplating on it)?						
8.	क्या आप ईश्वर की निकटता से संतुष्ट महसूस करती थीं /हैं?	Did/Do you feel satisfied by closeness to God?						
9.	क्या आपको लगता था/है की आपका जन्म किसी उद्देश्य के लिए हुआ है?	Did/Do you feel that you have been born for some great objective?						

10	क्या आप विश्वास करती थीं/हैं कि संकट के समय भगवान आपके साथ होता है?	Did/Do you believe that God is with you in times of crisis?							
11	मैं अपने जीवन का आनंद लेती थीं/हैं।	I enjoyed/enjoy my life.							
12	भगवान हमसे प्यार करता था/है और रक्षा करता था/है।	God loved/loves us and He protected/protects us.							
13	क्या आप मानती थीं/हैं कि गर्भ में पल रहा शिशु ईश्वर का प्रतिनिधि होता है?	Did/Do you agree that the baby developing in your womb is a representative of God?							
14	क्या आप नियमित आरती करती थीं/हैं?	Did/Do you perform aarti (singing hymns praising God) regularly?							
15	क्या आप भोजन बनाने, परोसने एवं खाने के पूर्व उसे अभिमंत्रित/ऊर्जावान बनाती थीं/हैं?	Did/Do you sanctify/energize your food through mantras/prayers while cooking, serving and before consuming it?							
16	क्या आप आत्म स्वरूप के रूप में प्रकाश का ध्यान करती थीं/हैं?	Did/Do you meditate on light as a reflection of your own self?							
17	क्या आप स्वयं के जीवन से संतुष्ट थीं/हैं?	Were/Are you satisfied with your life?							

Participant's Name and Sign प्रतिभागी का नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर:

Field Volunteer's Name and Sign क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता का नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर:

Annexure-6
(Questionnaire - Child Milestones - From Birth Till Five Years)

बच्चे की शारीरिक मानसिक विकास तालिका
Questionnaire – Child Milestones

बच्चे का नाम Child's Name: जन्मतिथि Date of Birth:

माता का नाम Mother's Name: सम्पर्क सूत्र Phone:

जिला District: प्रान्त State:.....

Activity	गतिविधि	बच्चे की उम्र (दिन/महीने) Child's age (Days/Months)
Calms down when spoken to or picked up	बात करने या उठाए जाने पर शांत हो जाते हैं	
Looks at your face	आपका चेहरा देखता है	
Seems happy to see you when you walk up to her	जब आप उसके पास जाते हैं तो आपको देखकर खूश होता है	
Smiles when you talk to or smile at her	जब आप उससे बात करते हैं या मुस्कुराते हैं तो वह मुस्कुराता है	
Makes sounds other than crying	रोने के अलावा और भी आवाज़ें निकालता है	
Reacts to loud sounds	तेज आवाज़ पर प्रतिक्रिया देता है	
Watches you as you move	जब आप गतिविधि करते हैं तो आपको देखता है	
Looks at a toy for several seconds	खिलौने को कुछ सेकंड के लिए देखता है	
Holds head up when on tummy	पेट के बल लेटने पर सिर ऊपर करता है	
Moves both arms and both legs	दोनों हाथों और दोनों पैरों को हिलाता है	
Opens hands briefly	संक्षेप में हाथ खोलता है	
Smiles on his own to get your attention	आपका ध्यान आकर्षित करने के लिए खुद मुस्कुराता है	
Chuckles (not yet a full laugh) when you try to make her laugh	जब आप उसे हँसाने की कोशिश करते हैं तो हँसता है (अभी तक पूरी हँसी नहीं)	
Looks at you, moves, or makes sounds to get or keep your attention	आपका ध्यान आकर्षित करने या बनाए रखने के लिए आपकी ओर देखता है, हिलता-डुलता है या आवाज करता है	
Makes sounds like "oooo", "aahh" (cooing)	"ऊ", "आह" (गुटगू करना) जैसी आवाज़ें निकालता है	

Makes sounds back when you talk to him	जब आप उससे बात करते हैं तो आवाज़ करके प्रतिक्रिया देता है	
Turns head towards the sound of your voice	आपकी आवाज़ की ओर सिर घुमाता है	
If hungry, opens mouth when she sees breast or bottle	भूख लगे तो स्तन या बोतल देखकर मुँह खोलता है	
Looks at his hands with interest	अपने हाथों को दिलचस्पी से देखता है	
Holds head steady without support when you are holding her	जब आप उसे गोद में लिए हुए हों तो सिर को बिना सहारे के स्थिर रखता है	
Holds a toy with both hand (bidexterous) when you put it in his hand	जब आप उसके हाथ में एक खिलौना रखते हैं तो उसे पकड़ता है	
Uses her arm to swing at toys	खिलौनों को घुमाने के लिए अपने हाथ का उपयोग करता है	
Brings hands to mouth	मुँह में हाथ डालता है	
Pushes up onto elbows/forearms when on tummy	जब पेट के बल लेटा हो तो कोहनियों/कलाईयों के बल खूद को उठाता है	
Knows familiar people	परिचित लोगों को जानता है	
Likes to look at himself in a mirror	खूद को आईने में देखना पसंद करता है	
Laughs	हँसता है	
Takes turns making sounds with you	आपके साथ-साथ आवाज़ें निकालता है बा, पा, गा (mono syllable)	
Blows "raspberries" (sticks tongue out and blows)	"कुलबुलाहट" जैसी आवाज़ें निकालता है (जीभ बाहर निकालकर होंठों में दबाकर जोर से हवा निकालना)	
Makes squealing noises	कर्कश आवाज़ें निकालता है	
Puts things in her mouth to explore them	चीजों के बारे में जानने के लिए अपने मुँह में डालती है	
Reaches to grab a toy he wants	जो उसे चाहिए उस खिलौने को लेने के लिए पहुँचता है	
Closes lips to show she doesn't want more food	यह दिखाने के लिए होंठ बंद करता है कि उसे और खाना नहीं चाहिए	
Rolls from tummy to back	पेट से पीठ तक रोल करता है	
Pushes up with straight arms when on tummy	पेट के बल सीधे हाथों से ऊपर उठता है	
Leans on hands to support himself when sitting)	बैठने पर खूद को सहारा देने के लिए हाथों पर झुक जाता है	
Is shy, clingy, or fearful around strangers	अजनबियों के आसपास शर्मीला है, चिपक जाता है या भयभीत होता है	

Shows several facial expressions, like happy, sad, angry, and surprised	चेहरे के कई भाव दिखाता है, जैसे खुश, उदास, क्रोधित, और आश्चर्यचकित	
Looks when you call her name	जब आप उसका नाम पुकारते हैं तो देखता है	
Reacts when you leave (looks, reaches for you, or cries)	जब आप बाहर जाते हैं तो प्रतिक्रिया देता है (देखता है, आपकी ओर बाँहें फैलाता है या रोता है)	
Smiles or laughs when you play peek-a-boo	जब आप छिपकर उसकी ओर देखने का खेल खेलते हैं तो मुस्कराता या हँसता है	
Makes different sounds like “mamamama” and “babababa”	"मामामा" और "बाबाबाबा" जैसी अलग-अलग आवाज़ें निकालता है	
Lifts arms up to be picked up	उठाए जाने के लिए हाथ ऊपर करता है	
Looks for objects when dropped out of sight (like his spoon or toy)	दृष्टि से दूर होने पर वस्तुओं की तलाश करता है (जैसे उसका चम्मच या खिलौना)	
Bangs two things together	दो चीजों को आपस में टकराता है	
Gets to a sitting position by herself	अपने आप बैठ जाता है	
Moves things from one hand to her other hand	चीजों को एक हाथ से दूसरे हाथ में ले जाता है	
Uses fingers to “rake” food towards himself	भोजन को अपनी ओर खींचकर लाने के लिए उंगलियों का उपयोग करता है	
Sits without support	बिना सहारे के बैठता है	
Plays games with you, like pat-a-cake	आपके साथ गेम खेलता है, जैसे गाने की धुन पर आपस में ताली बजाना या घघआ मन्ना जैसे खेल	
Waves “bye-bye”	हाथ हिलाकर "बाय-बाय" करता है	
Calls a parent “mama” or “dada” or another special name	माता-पिता को "मम्मा" या "बब्बा" या किसी अन्य विशेष नाम से पुकारता है	
Understands “no” (pauses briefly or stops when you say it)	"ना" को समझता है (आपके कहने पर थोड़ा रुकता है या बिल्कल रुक जाता है)	
Puts something in a container, like a block in a cup	कंटेनर में कुछ डालता है, जैसे एक कप में एक ब्लॉक	
Looks for things he sees you hide, like a toy under a blanket	उन चीजों की तलाश करता है जिन्हें वह आपको छिपाता हुआ देखता है, जैसे कि आप कम्बल के नीचे एक खिलौने को छिपाते हैं	
Pulls up to stand	खड़े होने के लिए खूद को ऊपर की ओर खींचता है	
Walks, holding on to furniture	फर्नीचर को पकड़े हुए चलता है	
Drinks from a cup without a lid, as you hold it	आपके हाथ से पकड़े हुए, बिना ढक्कन वाले प्याले से पीता है	
Picks things up between thumb and pointer finger, like small bits of food	अंगूठे और तर्जनी के बीच चीजों को उठाता है, जैसे भोजन के छोटे टुकड़े	
Copies other children while playing, like taking toys out of a container when another child does	खेलते समय अन्य बच्चों की नकल करता है, जैसे किसी अन्य बच्चे द्वारा खिलौनों को कंटेनर से बाहर निकालना	
Shows you an object she likes	आपको वह उसकी पसंद की वस्तु दिखाता है	

Claps when excited	उत्साहित होने पर ताली बजाता है	
Hugs stuffed doll or other toy	रूई से भरे खिलौने या अन्य खिलौने को गले लगाता है	
Shows you affection (hugs, cuddles, or kisses you)	आपको स्नेह दिखाता है (गले लगाना, चिपकना, या आपको चुम्बना)	
Tries to say one or two words besides "mama" or "dada," like "ba" for ball or "da" for dog	मम्मा" या "बब्बा" के अलावा एक या दो शब्द कहने की कोशिश करता है, जैसे गेंद के लिए "बो" या कत्ते के लिए "डो"	
Looks at a familiar object when you name it	जब आप किसी परिचित वस्तु का नाम लेते हैं तो वह देखता है	
Follows directions given with both a gesture and words. For example, he gives you a toy when you hold out your hand and say, "Give me the toy."	हावभाव और शब्दों, दोनों के साथ दिए गए निर्देशों का पालन करता है। उदाहरण के लिए, जब आप अपना हाथ आगे कर के कहते हैं, "मुझे खिलौना दो", तो वह आपको एक खिलौना देता है।	
Points to ask for something or to get help	कुछ माँगने या मदद पाने के लिए उंगली से इशारा करता है।	
Tries to use things the right way, like a phone, cup, or book	चीजों को सही तरीके से इस्तेमाल करने की कोशिश करता है, जैसे फोन, कप या किताब/कंकड़ों को कप में डाल सकता है।	
Stacks at least two small objects, like blocks	कम से कम दो छोटी वस्तुओं को एक के ऊपर एक रखता है, जैसे कि ब्लॉक	
Takes a few steps on his own	अपने दम पर कुछ कदम उठाता है	
Uses fingers to feed herself some food	खुद कुछ खाने के लिए उंगलियों का इस्तेमाल करता है	
Moves away from you, but looks to make sure you are close by	आपसे दूर जाता है, लेकिन यह सुनिश्चित करता है कि आप करीब हैं	
Points to show you something interesting	आपको कुछ दिलचस्प दिखाने के लिए उंगली से इशारा करता है	
Puts hands out for you to wash them	हाथ धोने के लिए आगे करता है	
Looks at a few pages in a book with you	आपके साथ किसी किताब के कुछ पन्ने देखता है	
Helps you dress him by pushing arm through sleeve or lifting up foot	आस्तीन के बाहर हाथ निकालकर या पैर ऊपर उठाकर खुद तैयार होने में आपकी सहायता करता है	
Tries to say three or more words besides "mama" or "dada"	"ममा" या "डैडा" के अलावा तीन या अधिक शब्द कहने का प्रयास करता है	
Follows one-step directions without any gestures, like giving you the toy when you say, "Give it to me."	बिना किसी इशारों के एक-चरणीय के निर्देशों का पालन करता है, जैसे कि जब आप कहते हैं, "मुझे दो।"	
Copies you doing chores, like sweeping with a broom	आपके द्वारा किए जाने वाले कामों की नकल करता है, जैसे झाड़ू लगाना	
Plays with toys in a simple way, like pushing a toy car	खिलौनों के साथ सरल तरीके से खेलता है, जैसे किसी छोटी कार को धक्का देना	
Walks without holding on to anyone or anything	किसी व्यक्ति या चीज को पकड़े बिना चलता है	
Scribbles	आड़ी-तिरछी रेखाएँ बनाता है	
Drinks from a cup without a lid and may spill sometimes	बिना ढक्कन वाले प्याले से पीता है और कभी-कभी गिरा सकता है	

Feeds herself with her fingers	अपनी उंगलियों से खूद खाता है	
Tries to use a spoon	चम्मच का उपयोग करने की कोशिश करता है	
Climbs on and off a couch or chair without help	बिना मदद के सोफे या कुर्सी पर चढ़ता-उतरता है	
Notices when others are hurt or upset, like pausing or looking sad when someone is crying	जब दूसरों को चोट लगती है या परेशान होते हैं तो ध्यान देता है, जैसे किसी के रोने पर रुकना या उदास दिखना	
Looks at your face to see how to react in a new situation	नई स्थिति में कैसे प्रतिक्रिया दी जाए यह देखने के लिए आपके चेहरे को देखता है	
Points to things in a book when you ask, like "Where is the bear?"	जब आप पूछते हैं जैसे "भालू कहाँ है?", तो किताब में चीजों की ओर इशारा करता है	
Says at least two words together, like "More milk."	कम से कम दो शब्द एक साथ कहता है, जैसे "ज्यादा दूध।"	
Points to at least two body parts when you ask him to show you	जब आप उसे आपको अंग दिखाने के लिए कहते हैं तो शरीर के कम से कम दो अंगों की ओर इशारा करता है	
Uses more gestures than just waving and pointing, like blowing a kiss or nodding yes	सिर्फ हाथ हिलाने और इशारा करने से ज्यादा चेष्टाओं का उपयोग करता है, जैसे चुंबन देना या हाँ में सिर हिलाना	
Holds something in one hand while using the other hand; for example, holding a container and taking the lid off	दूसरे हाथ का उपयोग करते समय एक हाथ में कुछ पकड़ता है; उदाहरण के लिए, कंटेनर को पकड़कर ढक्कन खोलना	
Tries to use switches, knobs, or buttons on a toy	खिलौने की स्विच, नॉब या बटन का उपयोग करने की कोशिश करता है	
Plays with more than one toy at the same time, like putting toy food on a toy plate	एक ही समय में एक से अधिक खिलौनों के साथ खेलता है, जैसे टॉय प्लेट पर टॉय फूड रखना	
Kicks a ball	गेंद को लात मारता है	
Runs	दौड़ता है	
Walks (not climbs) up a few stairs with or without help	मदद के साथ या बिना कुछ सीढ़ियों पर चलकर आगे बढ़ता है (चढ़ता नहीं है)	
Eats with a spoon	चम्मच से खाता है	
Plays next to other children and sometimes plays with them	अन्य बच्चों के आसपास खेलता है और कभी-कभी उनके साथ खेलता है	
Shows you what she can do by saying, "Look at me!"	"मुझे देखो!" कह कर वह आपको दिखाता है कि वह क्या कर सकता है।	
Follows simple routines when told, like helping to pick up toys when you say, "Its clean-up time."	बताए जाने पर सरल दिनचर्या का पालन करता है, जैसे जब आप कहते हैं, "यह साफ-सफाई का समय है, तब खिलौने लेने में मदद करना।"	
Says about 50 words	लगभग 50 शब्द बोल सकता है	
Says two or more words, with one action word, like "Doggie run"	एक क्रिया-शब्द के साथ दो या दो से अधिक शब्द कहता है, जैसे "कुत्ता भागा"	
Names things in a book when you point and ask, "What is this?"	जब आप किताब में इंगित कर के पूछते हैं, "यह क्या है?" तब नाम बताता है	

Says words like "I," "me," or "we"	"मैं", "मेरा", या "हम" जैसे शब्द कहता है	
Uses things to pretend, like feeding a block to a doll as if it were food	दिखावा करने के लिए चीजों का उपयोग करता है, जैसे किसी गुड़िया को ब्लॉक खिलाना जैसे कि वह भोजन हो	
Shows simple problem-solving skills, like standing on a small stool to reach something	सरल समस्या-समाधान कौशल दिखाता है, जैसे किसी चीज़ तक पहुँचने के लिए एक छोटे स्टूल पर खड़ा होना	
Follows two-step instructions like "Put the toy down and close the door."	दो-चरणीय निर्देशों का पालन करता है जैसे "खिलौना नीचे रखो और दरवाजा बंद करो।"	
Shows he knows at least one color, like pointing to a red crayon when you ask, "Which one is red?"	दिखाता है कि वह कम से कम एक रंग जानता है, जैसे कि जब आप पूछते हैं, "लाल क्रेयॉन कहाँ है?" तब लाल रंग के क्रेयॉन की ओर इशारा करता है	
Uses hands to twist things, like turning doorknobs or unscrewing lids	चीजों को मोड़ने के लिए हाथों का उपयोग करता है, जैसे कि दरवाजे की कुंडी मोड़ना या ढक्कन खोलना	
Takes some clothes off by himself, like loose pants or an open jacket	कुछ कपड़े अपने आप उतार देता है, जैसे ढीली पैंट या खुली जैकेट	
Jumps off the ground with both feet	दोनों पैरों से जमीन से कूदता है	
Turns book pages, one at a time, when you read to her	जब आप उसे पढ़कर सुनाते हैं, तब एक-एक करके किताब के पन्ने पलटता है	
Calms down within 10 minutes after you leave her, like at a childcare drop off	आपके उससे दूर जाने के 10 मिनट के भीतर शांत हो जाता है, जैसे चाइल्डकेअर ड्रॉप में छोड़ना	
Notices other children and joins them to play	अन्य बच्चों को नोटिस करता है और उन्हें खेल में शामिल करता है	
Talks with you in conversation using at least two back-and-forth exchanges	कम से कम दो बार हाथ को आगे-पीछे करके आपसे बातचीत करता है	
Asks "who," "what," "where," or "why" questions, like "Where is mommy/daddy?"	"कौन", "क्या", "कहाँ", या "क्यों" प्रश्न पूछता है, जैसे "मम्मा/पप्पा कहाँ हैं?"	
Says what action is happening in a picture or book when asked, like "running," "eating," or "playing"	पूछे जाने पर किसी चित्र या पुस्तक में क्या क्रिया हो रही है वह बताता है, जैसे "दौड़ना", "खाना", या "खेलना"	
Says first name, when asked	पूछे जाने पर प्रथम नाम कहता है	
Talks well enough for others to understand, most of the time	ज्यादातर समय दूसरों को समझने के लिए पर्याप्त रूप से बात करता है	
Draws a circle, when you show him how	जब आप उसे दिखाते हैं कि कैसे गोल आकार बनाना है, तब उसे बनाता है	
Avoids touching hot objects, like a stove, when you warn her	आपके उसे चेतावनी देने पर चूल्हे जैसी गर्म वस्तुओं को छूने से बचता है	
Strings items together, like large beads or macaroni	वस्तुओं को साथ जोड़ता है, जैसे बड़े मोती या मैकरोनी	
Puts on some clothes by himself, like loose pants or a jacket	कुछ कपड़े खुद पहनता है, जैसे ढीली पैंट या जैकेट	

Uses a fork	फोर्क का उपयोग करता है	
Pretends to be something else during play (teacher, superhero, dog)	खेल के दौरान कुछ और बनने का नाटक करता है (शिक्षक, सुपर हीरो, कुत्ता)	
Asks to go play with children if none are around, like "Can I play with Alex?"	अगर कोई आसपास नहीं है तो बच्चों के साथ खेलने जाने के लिए कहता है, जैसे "क्या मैं एलेक्स के साथ खेल सकता हूँ?"	
Comforts others who are hurt or sad, like hugging a crying friend	दूसरों को दिलासा देता है जब वे दुखी या उदास होते हैं, जैसे रोते हुए दोस्त को गले लगाना	
Avoids danger, like not jumping from tall heights at the playground	खतरे से बचता है, जैसे खेल के मैदान में ऊँचाई से न कूदने को कहना	
Likes to be a "helper"	"सहायक" बनना पसंद करता है	
Changes behavior based on where she is (place of worship, library, playground)	वह जगह (पूजा स्थल, पुस्तकालय, खेल का मैदान) के आधार पर व्यवहार बदलता है	
Says sentences with four or more words	चार या अधिक शब्दों वाले वाक्य कहता है	
Says some words from a song, story, or nursery rhyme	किसी गीत, कहानी या नर्सरी कविता से कुछ शब्द कहता है	
Talks about at least one thing that happened during his day, like "I played soccer."	उसके दिन के दौरान हुई कम से कम एक चीज़ के बारे में बात करता है, जैसे "मैंने फुटबॉल खेला।"	
Answers simple questions like "What is a coat for?" or "What is a crayon for?"	कोट का क्या उपयोग है?" जैसे सरल प्रश्नों के उत्तर देता है। या "क्रेयॉन का क्या उपयोग है?"	
Names a few colors of items	वस्तुओं के कुछ रंगों के नाम बताता है	
Tells what comes next in a well-known story	बताता है कि एक प्रसिद्ध कहानी में आगे क्या आता है	
Draws a person with three or more body parts	व्यक्ति के शरीर के तीन या अधिक अंगों का चित्र बनाता है	
Catches a large ball most of the time	ज्यादातर समय बड़ी गेंद पकड़ता है	
Serves himself food or pours water, with adult supervision	वयस्क व्यक्ति के निरीक्षण में स्वयं भोजन परोसता है या पानी देता है	
Unbuttons some buttons	कुछ बटन खोलता है	
Holds crayon or pencil between fingers and thumb (not a fist)	उंगलियों और अंगूठे के बीच क्रेयॉन या पेंसिल रखता है (मुट्ठी में नहीं)	
Follows rules or takes turns when playing games with other children	अन्य बच्चों के साथ खेल खेलते समय नियमों का पालन करता है या बारी-बारी से दांव लेता है	
Sings, dances, or acts for you	आपके लिए गाता है, नाचता है या अभिनय करता है	
Does simple chores at home, like matching socks or clearing the table after eating	घर के साधारण काम करता है, जैसे मोजे मिलाना या खाने के बाद टेबल साफ करना	
Tells a story she heard or made up with at least two events. For example, a cat was stuck in a tree and a firefighter saved it	एक कहानी सुनाता है जिसे उसने सुनी हो या कम से कम दो घटनाओं को साथ मिलाकर बनायी हो। उदाहरण के लिए, एक बिल्ली पेड़ पर फंस गई थी	

	और एक फायर फाइटर ने उसे बचा लिया	
Answers simple questions about a book or story after you read or tell it to him	किसी किताब या कहानी को पढ़ने या उसे बताने के बाद उसके बारे में सरल प्रश्नों के उत्तर देता है	
Keeps a conversation going with more than three back-and-forth exchanges	तीन से अधिक बार आगे-पीछे हाथ हिलाकर बातचीत जारी रखता है	
Uses or recognizes simple rhymes (bat-cat, ball-tall)	सरल कविता का उपयोग करता है या पहचानता है (काठी-लाठी, नानी-मोरनी)	
Counts to 10	10 तक गिनती करता है	
Names some numbers between 1 and 5 when you point to them	1 और 5 के बीच की कुछ संख्याओं को नाम दे जब आप उन्हें इंगित करते हैं	
Uses words about time, like “yesterday,” “tomorrow,” “morning,” or “night”	समय के बारे में शब्दों का उपयोग करता है, जैसे "बीते दिन", "कल", "सुबह", या "रात"	
Pays attention for 5 to 10 minutes during activities. For example, during story time or making arts and crafts (screen time does not count)	गतिविधियों के दौरान 5 से 10 मिनट तक ध्यान देता है। उदाहरण के लिए, कहानी के समय या कला और शिल्प बनाने के दौरान (स्कीन टाइम की गिनती नहीं होती है)	
Writes some letters in her name	उसके नाम के कुछ अक्षर लिखता है	
Names some letters when you point to them	जब आप उन्हें इंगित करते हैं तो कुछ अक्षरों को नाम देता है	
Buttons some buttons	कुछ बटन बंद करता है	
Hops on one foot	एक पैर पर उछलता है	

माता का नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर **Mother's Name and Sign:**

क्षेत्रीय कार्यकर्ता का नाम एवं हस्ताक्षर **Field Volunteer's Name and Sign:**